

**THE CLASSICAL-GENRE PAINTINGS OF
JOHN WILLIAM GODWARD:
FROM ARCHAEOLOGY TO ARCHETYPES**

by

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**A dissertation submitted in conformity with the requirements
for the Master's Degree in Fine and Decorative Art**

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EDITORIAL NOTE ON THIS 2026 DIGITAL REVISION

This is the definitive, restored digital version of my dissertation, originally written in 2007 and submitted to Sotheby's Institute of Art—London, where a bound copy is permanently kept in the institution's library. Except for this note, the text, arguments, and pagination remain unchanged from the original printed manuscript, and reflect the scholarship available at the time. I have corrected several technical and typographical inconsistencies throughout, bringing formatting and punctuation into alignment with *The Chicago Manual of Style* in a few places where they deviated from it.

I also partially reconstructed the illustration plates, as the final versions created in QuarkXPress were lost. Where reconstruction was needed, I preserved the original layout decisions as closely as possible. These include rotating wide horizontal images ninety degrees to enlarge them for legibility. In a few instances I placed related illustrations side by side on the same page for ease of comparison. These are matters of design convention that *Chicago* does not specifically address.

I conducted the research for this project in London, drafting much of the text in a reading room at the British Library. I completed it in a flat on Gower Street in Bloomsbury, only blocks from the British Museum, near the historic birthplace of the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood, and not far from the auto-icon of Jeremy Bentham residing at University College London. I once raised a pint to him at the Jeremy Bentham, his namesake pub, just across the street.

Michael Allan Kodysz
Lakewood, Ohio
July 2026

ABSTRACT

John William Godward, active from the mid-1880s until 1922, was a British painter of classical-genre scenes featuring lovely models dressed as Graeco-Roman women. He has often been dismissed as a mere imitator of Sir Lawrence Alma-Tadema, an older painter renowned for his archaeologically-specific scenes of everyday ancient life. However, many of Godward's paintings exhibit a more Aesthetic mode of composition in which the female figure is central. This dissertation argues that Godward's body of work tends toward amoral archetypes of feminine beauty and away from archaeological specificity and implied moral meaning.

First, key terms are defined as Godward is positioned within the moral, philosophical, and stylistic vicissitudes of Victorian and Edwardian classical-subject painting. Next, the archaeological and moral foundations of Godward's works are established. Finally, the artist's depictions of classical women are described as either moral or amoral archetypes, and in their relation to Aesthetic, Symbolist, and traditional "high art" forms. Many of Godward's early compositions, those most derivative of Alma-Tadema, reflect Victorian values regarding women's role in society. Nonetheless, Godward has gained a modicum of respect as a highly-skilled painter of "dream icons." These iconic images are amoral archetypes of feminine beauty representing the balance of the artist's work.

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Hers is the head upon which all “the ends of the world are come,”
and the eyelids are a little weary. It is a beauty wrought out from within
upon the flesh, the deposit, little cell by cell, of strange thoughts
and fantastic reveries and exquisite passions.

— Walter Pater, *The Renaissance*, 1873

INTRODUCTION

Relatively little attention has been paid to the work of John William Godward (1861–1922), a British painter of classical-genre scenes featuring lovely models dressed as Graeco-Roman women. He was active, first in London and later in Rome, from 1887 until his death by suicide.¹ Art historian and Godward biographer Vern Grosvenor Swanson described him as “an excellent artist of the second level of art historical significance.”² Indeed, Godward’s relative obscurity is due in part to his frequent dismissal as an imitator of Sir Lawrence Alma-Tadema (1836–1912), a Dutch-born British painter who became famous during the early 1870s.

Alma-Tadema was renowned for the meticulous detail and archaeological specificity of his classical-genre scenes of Greece, Rome, and Egypt. Many of his compositions depict crowds of figures surrounded by elaborate architecture, as in 1894’s *Spring* (fig. 1). He was also known for paintings of classically-draped women in languorous poses, as well as for his female nudes, whose eroticism was barely disguised by their classical context.³ Alma-Tadema epitomised the “artist-antiquarian,” and holds a place as one of the most influential and successful classical-genre painters of the late-Victorian and Edwardian eras.⁴ Historian Richard Jenkyns cites Alma-Tadema’s classical subjects, which often depict domestic themes, to

¹ “By 1922, no one wanted [Godward’s] classical maidens any more, and he committed suicide by putting his head in a gas oven.” Christopher Wood, *Olympian Dreamers: Victorian Classical Painters, 1860–1914* (London: Constable, 1983), 247; For a full discussion of the circumstances surrounding Godward’s suicide and its aftermath, see Vern Grosvenor Swanson, *John William Godward: The Eclipse of Classicism* (Woodbridge, UK: Antique Collectors’ Club, 1998), 116–17, 120, 122–23.

² Swanson, *Godward*, 169.

³ Julian Treuherz, *Victorian Painting* (London: Thames and Hudson, 1993), 171.

⁴ French critic Robert de la Sizeranne originally used the term “artist-antiquarian” in a description of Alma-Tadema’s method. Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 28; Despite calling all historical periods “arbitrary constructions,” Richard Jenkyns defines the Victorian age as the period of Queen Victoria’s reign, 1837–1901. He considers “late Victorian” to extend from the late 1860s to the early 1880s, and “Edwardian” to begin well before the reign of King Edward VII, spanning from the mid 1880s to around 1910. Richard Jenkyns, *Dignity and Decadence: Victorian Art and the Classical Inheritance* (London: HarperCollins, 1991), xi.

describe classical-genre painting as “the ‘daily-life-in-the-ancient-world’ school.”⁵

Several of Godward’s earliest paintings are clearly derivative of Alma-Tadema’s style. A side-by-side comparison of Alma-Tadema’s *The Oleander* from 1882 (fig. 2) with Godward’s *The Sweet Siesta of a Summer Day* from 1891 (fig. 3), for instance, reveals similarities of colouring, composition and subject matter. Nevertheless, the majority of Godward’s paintings are less compositionally complex. Many depict a single, idealised female figure idling amidst luxurious marble and fur, as in *Sweet Dreams* of 1901 (fig. 4). Swanson believes Godward’s work “reflects typical late-Victorian classical-subject painting.”⁶ He also points out that Godward’s paintings of so-called classical “beauties” exhibit the influence of several other famous classical-subject painters:

The intricate and crushed folds of classical garments show [an] ... affinity to Lord [Frederic] Leighton [1830–96], his fascination with the torpid poses of his single-figure compositions reflect Albert Joseph Moore [1841–93], while his architectural references emulate [Sir] Edward John Poynter [1836–1919].⁷

Godward is absent from the 1988 reprint of Jeremy Maas’s *Victorian Painters*, an authoritative survey including many lesser-known British painters besides more famous figures such as these.⁸ Indeed, scholars rarely mentioned the artist before the mid-1990s. Increased interest in Godward follows in the wake of the historical re-evaluation and financial re-valuation of Victorian painting in general that has occurred within the last few decades.⁹ In 1987, for example, Godward’s *Dolce Far*

⁵ Jenkyns, *Dignity and Decadence*, 233.

⁶ Swanson, *Godward*, 26.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ *Victorian Painters*, a survey all of the eras’ main stylistic classifications, was originally published in 1969. Godward is also missing from Lionel Lambourne’s similarly comprehensive work, 1999’s *Victorian Painting*.

⁹ Victorian painting had long been considered “a backwater of sentiment and outmoded academic convention that was bypassed by the mainstream of development in Western art.” “Victorian Painting,” Phaidon. <http://www.phaidon.com/Default.aspx/Web/victorian-painting-9780714843599> (accessed September 29, 2007).

Niente of 1904 (fig. 5) would have been considered successful had it brought £15,000 at auction. But in 1997—just ten years later and only ten years ago—Lord Andrew Lloyd-Webber purchased this same painting for a winning bid of £361,000.¹⁰

Numbers such as these would have surprised William Gaunt, the late art historian whose book *Victorian Olympus*, first printed in 1952, includes no mention of Godward. The artist does not figure into Gaunt’s story of the lives and works of the better-known British classical-subject painters: Leighton, Poynter, Moore, George Frederic Watts (1817–1904) and, of course, Alma-Tadema. Gaunt’s account remains one of the standard sources of information about these artists.

Christopher Wood offers a brief discussion of Godward in 1983’s *Olympian Dreamers*. Wood’s book is largely devoted to an analysis of the careers of five classical-subject painters, whom he calls “Olympians”—Alma-Tadema, Leighton, Poynter, John William Waterhouse (1849–1917), and Watts—to chart the passage of British classical-subject painting from its Victorian “heights” to its popular decline in the early twentieth century. Wood calls these waning years, from around 1900 to 1920, “The Twilight of the Gods.” Godward’s style, which came into its own during this time, is described as the least “banal” of all the artist’s peers.¹¹ The author confirms Godward’s reputation as a follower of Alma-Tadema, but he also claims that Godward’s painting sometimes achieves a “monumentality” comparable to Leighton.¹² Because Leighton is often considered the “grandest” of Victorian painters on a par with the Old Masters of the Italian Renaissance, this is no minor assessment.¹³

Historian Joseph A. Kestner, in his 1989 book *Mythology and Misogyny: The Social Discourse of Nineteenth-Century British Classical-Subject Painting*, takes a

¹⁰ Swanson, *Godward*, 78.

¹¹ Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 245.

¹² *Ibid.*, 247.

¹³ Jenkyns, *Dignity and Decadence*, 202, 222.

more cynical view of these artists. Kestner's argument is that patriarchal society used classical-subject painting as a tool of "cultural indoctrination" to bolster its authority over women.¹⁴ In Kestner's view, classical-subject painters reinforced the stereotypical roles of women in British society by comparing them with the "insidious" predecessor of ancient mythology.¹⁵ Images of Aphrodite, Siren, and Circe, for example, represent the female archetypes of goddess, prostitute, and "she-beast."¹⁶ Kestner argues that Alma-Tadema was a misogynist, and uses Godward's *Ismenia* (fig. 6) to illustrate a description of the latter's body of work as representing nothing more profound than a vapid "gallery of beauty."¹⁷

In the 1991 book *Dignity and Decadence: Victorian Art and the Classical Inheritance*, classics professor Richard Jenkyns is more even-handed than Kestner in discussing the major British classical-subject painters. Jenkyns argues that the idea of the classical past was as important to shaping the Victorian era as the idea of the Gothic. He examines a wide range of art, both "high" and "low," to trace the influence of classical Greece and Rome within the broader context of Victorian society. Although Jenkyns never mentions Godward, *Dignity and Decadence* contains extensive historical background.

A 1994 exhibition catalogue, *Heaven on Earth: The Religion of Beauty in Late Victorian Art* by Gail-Nina Anderson and Joanne Wright, also contains nothing about Godward. The book focuses instead on representations of beautiful women by Pre-Raphaelite and Symbolist painters active during the late-nineteenth and early-twentieth centuries. It also explores the ways in which these artists adapted Renaissance Christian forms to their own secular subject matter. Although the authors' discussion is

¹⁴ Joseph A. Kestner, *Mythology and Misogyny: The Social Discourse of Nineteenth-Century British Classical-Subject Painting* (London: University of Wisconsin Press, 1989), 15.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 6.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, 5, 6, 14.

¹⁷ Swanson, *Godward*, 89.

not about classical genre specifically, it provides invaluable insight into Godward's art. In forging connections between Renaissance images of saints and Madonnas and the "embowered maidens" and "enraptured beloveds" of the Pre-Raphaelites and Symbolists, Anderson and Wright lead the way toward the discovery of comparable origins for Godward's Graeco-Roman women.¹⁸

Writing respectively for the catalogues of separate art exhibitions, one held in 1996 and the other in 2003—and this time including Godward—art historians Elizabeth Prettejohn and Robyn Asleson both acknowledge Godward's reputation as an Alma-Tadema "imitator."¹⁹ Nevertheless, each praises Godward for his highly-skilled renderings of archaeological details. Prettejohn ascribes the repetitive nature of Godward's subject matter largely to his marketing acumen, not to misogynistic intent or lack of imagination or talent.²⁰

Indeed, Godward's motives and psychological makeup can only be surmised. One of the difficulties in researching this painter is a lack of primary sources, since his immediate family destroyed most of his personal papers shortly after his death. Not even a photograph of the artist is known to survive. The only major secondary source devoted to Godward is Vern Grosvenor Swanson's *John William Godward: The Eclipse of Classicism*, a 1997 biography and catalogue raisonné.²¹ Here, Swanson

¹⁸ Gail-Nina Anderson and Joanne Wright, *Heaven on Earth: The Religion of Beauty in Late Victorian Art: The Catalogue of an Exhibition at the Djanogly Art Gallery*, University of Nottingham Arts Centre (London: University of Nottingham Arts Centre, 1994), 23.

¹⁹ Godward's 1909 painting *At the Thermae* was included as *A Roman Woman* in the exhibition "Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century" shown at Bristol City Museum and Art Gallery from 3 May to 23 June 1996. His *Dolce far Niente (A Pompeian Fishpond)* of 1904 was included in the exhibition "Pre-Raphaelite and Other Masters: The Andrew Lloyd Webber Collection" shown at the Royal Academy of Arts, London, from 20 September to 12 December 2003.

²⁰ Elizabeth Prettejohn, "Recreating Rome in Victorian Painting: From History to Genre," in *Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century*, ed. Catharine Edwards and Michael Liversidge (London: Merrell Holberton, 1996), 67.

²¹ Swanson himself is the author of the only other sources published specifically about Godward. One is an article entitled "John William Godward: The Death of Classicism" appearing in a 1996 issue of the *Classical Realist Quarterly*. The other is an article entitled "Godward and the Death of Greco-Roman Painting" published online in 2000. The later article appears to be an electronic incarnation of the earlier one, and incorporates material from the introduction to Swanson's book, as

presents some useful insights regarding Godward's personality. The author bases his characterisation primarily upon information gleaned from interviews with descendants of the painter's relatives and other limited evidence.

Swanson thoroughly depicts Godward's style within its overall historical context and explains his relation to other painters and artistic movements that existed during the span of the artist's career. It should be noted that Swanson does not glorify Godward or attempt to elevate him above his status as a relatively minor artist. Swanson's discussion seems, overall, balanced. Nevertheless, the author does encourage a "re-examination" of Godward's historical importance as the best of the last in the dying tradition of British classical-subject painting. "In Godward's work," wrote Swanson, "we see the final summation of half a millennium of classical antique influence on Western painting."²² As such, Godward's body of work is an important cultural milestone.

Limited sources notwithstanding, the greatest challenge in taking up Swanson's call to re-examine Godward lies in describing his paintings stylistically. Certainly, many painters and types of painting defy easy categorisation, so problems of definition are not at all unique to Godward. Attempts to categorise Victorian and Edwardian British classical-subject painters, however, are particularly elusive. George Frederic Watts, for example, one of Wood's classical-subject "Olympians," painted allegorical subjects taken from classical mythology. Watts, along with Edward Burne-Jones (1833–98) and Dante Gabriel Rossetti (1828–82), is

well as from a chapter entitled "The Death of the Classical Subject Tradition." See Swanson, *Godward*, 13–15, 145–51; Swanson's book precedes the online article by three years, but the latter states "to date no more than four paragraphs have been published on [Godward]." Vern Grosvenor Swanson, "Godward and the Death of Greco-Roman Painting," *Art Renewal Center* (2000), <http://www.artrenewal.org/articles/2000/Godward/godward2.asp> (accessed April 9, 2007).

²² Swanson, *Godward*, 13; Joseph A. Kestner believes, "[Godward's] art and that of [fellow painter Henry] Ryland are the most glaring examples of classical-subject painting degenerating into galleries of beauty. This movement represents a severe decline in the classical-subject tradition as women are reduced to meaningless icons." Quoted in Swanson, *Godward*, 135.

considered a pioneer of the allusive art of the Symbolist Movement.²³ Burne-Jones and Rossetti belonged to the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood, whose members admired, and sometimes emulated, the style of fifteenth-century Italian art from before the time of Raphael. Yet, Burne-Jones and Rossetti often painted classical and mediaeval subjects.

In *Dignity and Decadence*, Jenkyns includes Burne-Jones and Rossetti along with Alma-Tadema, Leighton, Poynter, and Watts in his discussion of British classical-subject painting.²⁴ Unlike the four latter painters, Godward was not a member of Britain's "official" art establishment, the Royal Academy, even though he occasionally exhibited work in its prestigious Summer Exhibition. Nor was he a member of any anti-establishment stylistic movement such as the Pre-Raphaelites, as were Burne-Jones and Rossetti. More than many of his contemporaries, however, Godward was devoted to the "cult" of feminine beauty, a theme that was central to the Aesthetic Movement.²⁵

British essayist and critic Walter Pater (1839–94) formulated Aestheticism's two key concepts in a highly-influential theory published in 1877. First, the essence of art is amoral, lying in its material form and not the subject or meaning of its content; and second, that art is superior to nature.²⁶ In rejecting the moral and didactic role of art and emphasising form over content, Aestheticism follows the principal known as "art-for-art's sake."²⁷

Swanson describes Godward's style only nebulously, but never as art-for-art's sake. On the one hand, the author places it with the "formal classicism" of Leighton,

²³ Edward Lucie-Smith, *Symbolist Art* (1972; repr., London: Thames and Hudson, 1995), 50.

²⁴ Jenkyns, *Dignity and Decadence*, 199.

²⁵ Treuherz, *Victorian Painting*, 142; For a detailed discussion of the origins and philosophy of the Aesthetic Movement and its impact on British painting, see *ibid.*, 131–36.

²⁶ Treuherz, *Victorian Painting*, 132.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, 132–33.

and on the other with archaeological “reconstructionalists” such as Alma-Tadema and Poynter.²⁸ Although Swanson identifies the “torpid poses” of Godward’s figures with those of Albert Moore, he does not mention Godward at all in relation to an “aesthetic-classicism movement.”²⁹ Swanson’s description of “aesthetic classicism” is vague, but it seems to refer to a strand of British classical-subject painting influenced by Aestheticism and most typified by the paintings of Moore.³⁰ Under this guise, classical-subject paintings belonging to Swanson’s “aesthetic-classicism” convention would exhibit characteristics of Aestheticism’s art-for-art’s-sake principle.

Thus, Swanson has largely dismissed the idea that Godward’s work exhibits an amoral and decorative tendency that is often described as Aesthetic. To be sure, Godward’s classical-genre paintings are grounded in the moral, didactic, and technical conventions of British classical-subject painting. This dissertation will argue that Godward’s body of work tends toward amoral archetypes of feminine beauty and away from the archaeological specificity and implied morality of classical genre. Amorality in this context means the absence of any discernable moral or religious agenda; subjects that are not specifically meant to “ennoble” the viewer.

Although the “cult” of feminine beauty was central to both Godward and the Aesthetic Movement, there is no suggestion here that Godward harboured any conscious or subconscious desire to identify himself or his art with Aestheticism. This is not a feminist argument, even though Kestner claims that classical-subject painting was a misogynistic activity, and paintings described as Aesthetic often objectify the female form. Paintings by Moore will be discussed, but this is not an effort to align

²⁸ Swanson identifies several “stylistic conventions” in British classical-subject painting, which he outlines using the names of some of the better-known painters in a list of 118 comprising what he calls the “late classical milieu.” Swanson, *Godward*, 141.

²⁹ Despite Swanson’s extensive research, he rarely provides in-depth analysis of individual works to substantiate his characterisation of Godward’s style. *Ibid.*

³⁰ Swanson avoids the word “Aesthetic” entirely as a proper name; “Aesthetic,” “Aestheticism,” and “Aesthetic Movement” never appear in his book.

Godward's style specifically with Swanson's "aesthetic classicism."

Using an object-based approach over the course of the next three chapters, comparative works to be examined will include those by artists commonly recognised as immediate influences upon Godward's style, as well as others that are somewhat more speculative. Chapter 1 will introduce the moral, philosophical, and stylistic vicissitudes of British classical-subject painting against which Godward's art, in some sense, may be measured. It will also outline Godward's early artistic development amongst two of his peers. Although Swanson named eight of Godward's peers as most stylistically similar to him, only the two with whom he had the advantage of daily contact will be discussed.³¹ Chapter 2 will establish the archaeological and moral foundations of Godward's art within the context of classical-genre paintings by Alma-Tadema and Poynter. In Chapter 3, Godward's classical women will be seen as either moral or amoral archetypes, depending upon the ways they relate to their socio-material environments. They will also be positioned in relation to Aesthetic, Symbolist, and traditional "high art" forms. Godward will remain an enigmatic figure throughout, yet our insight into his art may be nonetheless enriched.

³¹ For a discussion of these "Very Last Classicists," see Swanson, *Godward*, 141, 144–45.

Chapter 1

Historical Background

Pictorial art addresses itself directly to the sense of sight; to the emotions and the intellect only indirectly. ... Therefore perfection of forms and colours—beauty, in a word—should be the prime object of pictorial art. Having this, it has the chief requisite; and spiritual, intellectual beauty are contingent on this, are something thrown into the bargain.

— Sidney Colvin, *Fortnightly Review*, 1867

Fading interest in British classical-subject painting early in the twentieth century can be traced to several causes. The *fin-de-siècle* deaths of some of its most influential practitioners, including Leighton, Moore, and Watts, marked the end of an era. Additionally, the death of Queen Victoria in 1901 deprived the Royal Academy of one of its most generous supporters. Around this time, the women's rights movement gained socio-political influence as it became increasingly more organised. Feminists believed that portrayals of women in paintings such as Godward's reinforced traditional constructions of gender, and viewed them with hostility.¹

Another important cause of British classical-subject painting's demise, the aggressive criticism of academic art by avant-garde modernists, arose during the twentieth century's second decade. Members of modernist British art movements such as the Bloomsbury Group, the Camden Town Group, the London Group, and the Vorticists, as Swanson put it, "conspired to demolish their conservative opposition."² To Roger Fry (1866–1934), a critic associated with the Bloomsbury Group, works such as Alma-Tadema's *Spring* epitomised all that was wrong with classical-subject painting in the Western academic tradition.³ In a 1913 article published in

¹ Swanson, *Godward*, 145.

² *Ibid.*, 148.

³ For a discussion of "official" art's foremost detractors, Clive Bell (1881–1964) and Roger Fry, see S.K. Tillyard, *The Impact of Modernism, 1900–1920: Early Modernism and the Arts and Crafts Movement in Edwardian England* (London: Routledge, 1988), 215–17.

the *Nation* magazine, Fry used Alma-Tadema's work as a target of derision, alluding to the ineffectiveness of British classical-genre painting as a modern mode of artistic expression:

[Alma-Tadema's] art ... demands nothing from the spectator beyond the almost unavoidable knowledge that there was such a thing as the Roman Empire, whose people were very rich, very luxurious, and, in retrospect at least, agreeably wicked. ... Sir Lawrence proceeded to satisfy all the futile inquiries that indolent curiosity might make about the domestic belongings and daily trifles of those people.⁴

For Godward and several other London painters who began their careers in the 1880s, Alma-Tadema's "futile inquiries" had been a key source of inspiration. Amongst them were George Lawrence Bulleid (1858–1933) and Henry Ryland (1859–1924), who were friends and peer-mentors of the young Godward. The three artists occupied neighbouring ateliers at Bolton Studios, 17 Gilston Road, between 1888 and 1889.⁵ As Swanson believes, "the influence that ... [these] and other Boltonites had on one another was seminal in their artistic growth."⁶ Indeed, studio props and costumes used in common amongst the painters provide evidence of close contact. The figures in Ryland's undated *By the Southern Sea* (fig. 7) and Godward's *Young Woman* of 1894 (fig. 8), for example, wear the same patterned girdles.

Although Godward, Bulleid, and Ryland may have received some formal training together, it is impossible to be certain. Swanson offers extensive speculation regarding the details of the artist's general education and specific art training, but documentation is lacking. Nevertheless, Swanson deduced that Godward might have trained part-time at the Royal Academy, Victorian Britain's foremost art school. Whilst

⁴ Fry's article appeared less than a year after Alma-Tadema's death. Roger Fry, "The Case of the Late Sir Lawrence Alma Tadema, O.M.," *The Nation*, (18 January 1913): 666–67, quoted in Swanson, *Godward*, 149.

⁵ Swanson, *Godward*, 32.

⁶ *Ibid.*

the Academy's prestige alone would have been a sufficient reason for Godward to attend, another was the presence of William Clarke Wontner (1857–1930), who began teaching there in 1885.⁷ The slightly-older Wontner was one of Godward's closest friends who, perhaps earlier, had been responsible for the younger artist's training.⁸ Visiting instructors to the Academy included the most famous classical-subject painters of the day—Alma-Tadema, Leighton, and Poynter—so if Godward did attend, he might have received at least some of his training directly from them.

Alma-Tadema, Leighton, and Poynter often used their classical settings as pretexts to paint idealised human subjects, especially women. Alma-Tadema's *The Favourite Poet* of 1888 (fig. 9), for example, features a beautiful woman in dreamy repose. Images of languorous “beauties”—idle, pensive, or asleep, and often overtly titillating—were ubiquitous in late-Victorian and Edwardian visual culture. The idea of the “fainting woman” arose from a complex set of socio-psychological factors, including the subjugation of women and the perceived threat that their active sexuality posed to patriarchal society.⁹ Languorous women as a motif in British painting crossed many stylistic boundaries, whilst the idea of woman-as-beautiful-object became the focus of a larger trend in British painting toward Aestheticism.

The *nouveau riche* were the Aesthetic Movement's primary supporters, and as Victorian society became increasingly secular throughout the nineteenth century, many worshipped the “cult” of art in place of religion.¹⁰ As art historian Robyn Asleson observed, “classicism and Aestheticism coalesced in the work of Albert Moore ... who conceived of his paintings as beautiful arrangements of beautiful things, without

⁷ Swanson, *Godward*, 23.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Dorothy Compton, “Dead Women and Byronic Men: Depictions of Beauty in the Victorian Era,” University of Michigan-Dearborn, <http://www.umd.umich.edu/casl/hum/eng/classes/434/charweb/VICTORIA.htm> (accessed July 25, 2007).

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 154–55.

meaning or moral.”¹¹ Moore’s *Battledore* of 1868–70 (fig. 10), for example, depicts a female figure draped and posed in the Graeco-Roman manner, holding nineteenth-century sporting equipment, and surrounded by “Anglo-Japanese décor:” fans, plants, and patterned drapery.¹² For Moore, paintings such as this functioned primarily as “aesthetic experiments” in which he used both human subjects and inanimate objects to explore pleasing combinations of composition and colour.¹³

Here the female figure averts her eyes, ready for objectification. An inanimate object like the reposing or sleeping woman, she remains powerless: she cannot engage the viewer as the viewer engages her. Moore’s figures are, as Asleson observed, “cyphers” or “blank slates onto which a wide range of meanings could be projected.”¹⁴ The idea of women as cyphers was not new to the Western tradition; the image of the female figure had long served the purposes of allegory. But, wrote Asleson, in late-nineteenth-century British society “this cypher-like quality also made women the most obvious vehicles for subjectless easel paintings.”¹⁵

Stereotypically associated with a pacific, private sphere in which harmony and beauty reigned, they “naturally” lent themselves to the value system that Aesthetic artists were advancing in reaction against the competitive commercial world.¹⁶

Moore’s Aesthetic style informed the work of Godward and his peers. However, most classical-subject painters of Godward’s generation diversified their work, motivated, perhaps, by profit, principle, or a desire for praise to paint Christian subjects. Bulleid’s *The Crucifixion* of 1904 (fig. 11), for instance, and Ryland’s

¹¹ Asleson, Robyn. “Academics and Classicists: Leighton, Alma-Tadema, Poynter, Moore and Others,” in *Pre-Raphaelite and Other Masters: The Andrew Lloyd Webber Collection*, ed. Michael Foster (London: Royal Academy of Arts, 2003), 188.

¹² Robyn Asleson, *Albert Moore* (London: Phaidon Press, 2000), 129.

¹³ Asleson, *Moore*, 129.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, 131.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

undated triptych *The Annunciation, the Good Shepherd and the Gleaner* (fig. 12), carry overt moral meaning. At the same time, Godward avoided Christian subject matter completely as his paintings of classical women became increasingly homogenous. Indeed, Swanson believes that the financially independent Godward painted for neither profit nor praise. That the artist rarely submitted work for exhibition at the Royal Academy seems to support this notion.¹⁷ Nevertheless, the sizable volume of correspondence between Godward and his art dealers does suggest some financial motive. Moreover, Swanson has refused to align the artist with the anti-commercial Aesthetic agenda of Moore; Godward was “too bourgeois.”¹⁸ In any case, is it fair to say, as Kestner might, that Godward’s “gallery of beauty” is devoid of moral or artistic merit?

For many in Victorian Britain, however, beauty and morality were inseparable. In an 1879 article published in the *Nineteenth Century* magazine, London writer Emilie Isabel Barrington (1841–1933) complained that “serious obstacles in the conditions of modern society” had engendered troubling circumstances: increasingly each year, large portions of the Royal Academy’s coveted exhibition space had been usurped by inferior work.¹⁹ These pieces, making no claims or pretensions to “high” art, obscured “better” work and had been born of primarily financial motives. Worse, through the unwitting appreciation of the masses, they served to perpetuate the bad

¹⁷ Swanson, *Godward*, 134.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ Emilie Isabel Barrington was a prominent figure of London’s Victorian art scene. She was a novelist, biographer, art critic, and editor who contributed articles to periodicals and journals such as the *Fortnightly Review* and the *Spectator*. A daughter of James Wilson (1805–60), who was a British politician and founder of the *Economist*, she received an upper-middle-class education. She was a neighbour and confidante of G.F. Watts and the wife of Russell Barrington, who was the son of British aristocrats and a mediator between Watts and the artist’s buyers. She was a friend of Leighton, Rossetti, and the artist Walter Crane (1845–1915). After the deaths of Leighton and Watts, she wrote authoritative biographies of both. She became an important benefactor of Leighton House, and her efforts were crucial to ensuring its designation as a museum. *Oxford Dictionary of National Biography*, (Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 2004), s.vv. “Barrington, Emilie Isabel.”

taste that, in her opinion, had become endemic.²⁰ However, Barrington did concede the fortunate existence of a few native “poet-painters” with a nod to Frederic Leighton, the Academy’s recently-elected president.²¹

Barrington was an admirer of Leighton, but her article gives little indication of her faith in the new president’s ability or intention to initiate reform; instead, she proposed her own solution. British artists, she asserted, should devote themselves exclusively to the production of a type of “true” art founded upon the highest ideal—that of eternal beauty.²² In making her case, she referred to the writings of the famed English author and critic, John Ruskin (1819–1900). Ruskin’s view was that the greatness of any society depends primarily upon the magnificence of its works.²³ He claimed that all men should base their efforts upon the highest moral principals, and that these efforts should be praised or reviled in direct proportion to the extent that they seem allied with or estranged from God.²⁴ Similarly, Barrington saw art’s main hope for salvation in its adherence to Christian principles.²⁵

As Gaunt observed, the classical painters’ pagan subject matter was, of all styles of British painting, “necessarily opposite to the Christian ideal” and, as such, the most susceptible to religious opposition.²⁶ Still, statesmen, scholars and academics, raised on the writings of Homer and the philosophy of Plato, could accept on principle the inherited visual standards of classical art and beauty whether they cared to understand

²⁰ E.I. Barrington, “Is a Great School of Art Possible in the Present Day?” *Nineteenth Century* (April 1879): 716.

²¹ Leighton held the Presidency of the Royal Academy from 1878 to 1896. *Ibid.*

²² *Ibid.*, 717.

²³ *Ibid.*, 716.

²⁴ Wendell V. Harris, “Ruskin’s Theoretic Practicality and the Royal Academy’s Aesthetic Idealism,” *Nineteenth-Century Literature* 52, No. 1 (June 1997): 88.

²⁵ Although Barrington did express a certain respect for the pagan genius of the ancient Greek sculptor Phidias, she objected to the “twisted” notions of the middle class that had led artists to turn away from religion. Barrington, “Great School,” 717, 721.

²⁶ William Gaunt, *Victorian Olympus* (London: Jonathan Cape, 1952. Revised ed., 1975) 83.

them or not.²⁷ Moreover, the Victorian *nouveau riche*, deplored by Barrington because they were less aesthetically discriminating than aristocratic buyers, had become classical-subject paintings' primary market. These new buyers were eager to decorate their stately homes, and images of classical civilisation offered a special allure as an escape from urban ugliness and the pressures of daily life. There were other attractions as well. According to historian William Gaunt, classical-subject painting "represented a world of cultured education which many a wealthy buyer, grown rich through manufacture and industry, had not known; and to some, maybe, it was a privileged peep behind the screen of clothes by which the human body was concealed."²⁸

Controversy about the merits of such painting arose largely from differing interpretations of Ruskin's "tangled" aesthetic theories of the moral role of beauty in art.²⁹ Barrington's Christian view—that morality in art should grow naturally from a devotion to Christian principles (i.e., Christian subjects)—was based largely on her interpretation of Ruskin. Conversely, British classical-subject painters such as Leighton, Alma-Tadema, and Watts were probably agnostic.³⁰

According to Kestner, "classical legend was a means of emancipation" by which these painters could "disassociate themselves from Christian belief."³¹ Even so, each felt a moral obligation to use his art as a means to "improve the world."³² Leighton's *Bath of Psyche* from 1890 (fig. 13), for example, is grounded not in Christian principles, but in the "ennobling" principle of balance found in idealised Greek forms.³³ Although potentially scandalous, this type of nude was generally well received by both the public and the critics because of its association with the classical world.

²⁷ Gaunt, *Victorian Olympus*, 83.

²⁸ *Ibid.*, 87.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, 80.

³⁰ Kestner, *Mythology and Misogyny*, 18.

³¹ *Ibid.*, 18–19

³² Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 17.

³³ *Ibid.*, 16.

Whilst Barrington herself might have admired Leighton's nude, she probably would have frowned upon Godward's *A Fair Reflection* (fig. 14), painted nine years later.³⁴ Godward's female figure resembles Leighton's, but the latter has morally "elevated" his nude by identifying her with the ancient Greek goddess Psyche, who personified the female soul. In some sense, both paintings may be considered voyeuristic, but Godward's contemporaries would not have viewed his mortal woman as ennobling. The artist has negated her connection to ancient mythology by naming his work for the optical effect of an inanimate object.

With paintings such as *A Fair Reflection*, Godward followed academic conventions in terms of his technical proficiency and interest in classical antiquity. However, classical-genre paintings such as this were not considered high art by Victorian standards. These standards followed the principles enumerated by the Royal Academy's first president, Sir Joshua Reynolds (1723–92), in his *Discourses* of 1769–90.³⁵ Where "history painting" stood at the summit of Reynolds's hierarchy of types, genre painting occupied the bottom.³⁶ As art historian Julian Treuherz explained, Reynolds's definition of history painting encompassed "ennobling" historical, religious, mythological, literary, or allegorical subjects:

[This] combination of an idealised, monumental style with heroic subject matter was often referred to as 'high art' [and was] expressed in an artistic language based on the work of ... a canon [of Old Masters].³⁷

Genre painting, which "dealt with the momentary and the particular," came to encompass "everyday" scenes of ancient life characterised by archaeologically-specific

³⁴ *A Fair Reflection* is shown in reverse for easier comparison.

³⁵ Treuherz, *Victorian Painting*, 10.

³⁶ *Ibid.*, 11.

³⁷ *Ibid.*

detail.³⁸ As this type of painting became increasingly popular during the Victoria era, paintings of “heroic” classical subjects diminished. According to Elizabeth Prettejohn, this situation led to the “drastic devaluation of Roman subject matter from history painting, at the summit of the hierarchy, to the humble category of genre painting.”³⁹

The descent of Roman-subject painting from the peak of Reynolds’s hierarchy parallels the descent of classical history and mythology overall from the heights of Victorian moral and aesthetic ideals. In *Dignity and Decadence*, Richard Jenkyns chronicles the slide of classical subjects and motifs from the upper-class heights past the middle-class “foothills,” further down toward the lowlands of British popular culture. The author cites funerary art, printed material, pub- and shop-front designs, and the façades of theatres like London’s Savoy to illustrate the ubiquity of classical subject and motifs at every level of Victorian taste.⁴⁰

Both Greece and Rome offered numerous literary and aesthetic examples; but in the Victorians’ view, the greatest prestige belonged to Hellas.⁴¹ Like the Renaissance masters before them, classical-subject painters of the nineteenth-century found their foremost passion in the heroics, nobility, and moral veracity of Homer.⁴² For many artists, the friezes from the Parthenon, removed from the Acropolis by Lord Elgin (1766–1841) and purchased for the British Museum in 1816, stood without peer as models of classical perfection. Leighton and Watts even had casts of the marbles installed in their studios.⁴³

Watts in particular, through the grandeur of timeless allegorical subjects in paintings such as *Love and Life* (fig. 15), devoted himself wholeheartedly to the

³⁸ Treuherz, *Victorian Painting*, 11.

³⁹ Prettejohn, “Recreating Rome,” 54.

⁴⁰ Jenkyns, *Dignity and Decadence*, 20–21.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, 17.

⁴² Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 19.

⁴³ The marbles were brought to London piecemeal between 1803 and 1812. Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 16.

emulation of Greek aesthetic ideals. Leighton also nurtured a personal vision of Hellenic beauty and form that eventually led him to abandon his youthful pursuit of mediaeval subjects. Works such as *Perseus on Pegasus Hastening to the Rescue of Andromeda* (fig. 16), painted between 1895 and 1896, illustrate Leighton's fondness for the idealised forms and heroic themes of Greek mythology. Where Watts had placed his allegorical figures within a mysterious, indistinct, and "clouded" atmosphere, Leighton sought to convey a dreamlike and dramatic mood by setting his subjects within a "timeless" but still vaguely classical environment.⁴⁴

Edward Poynter, Leighton's younger disciple, aspired to his master's example. Poynter introduced to Britain the first curricula incorporating nude study outside the Royal Academy during his tenure as Slade Professor of Fine Art at London's University College during the 1870s.⁴⁵ Poynter's Parisian training during the 1850s had convinced him of the benefits of drawing the human figure from life. It also exposed him to the severe style and archaeological concerns of French Neoclassicist painters such as Ingres, Gérôme, and David.⁴⁶ Poynter himself acknowledged in 1879 that his greatest mentor remained Leighton, "the friend and master who first directed my ambition, and whose precepts I never fail to recall."⁴⁷

The success of Poynter's *The Catapult* of 1868 (fig. 17) depended primarily upon the high degree of accuracy with which it portrayed the "particulars" of Roman engineering.⁴⁸ Prettejohn classifies *The Catapult* as an early example of classical-

⁴⁴ Watts hoped to infuse his works with a heightened sense of mystery and splendour. Julia Cartwright, "G.F. Watts, Royal Academician: His Life and Work," in "The Easter Art Annual for 1896," special issue, *Art Journal* (1896): 8; According to Jenkyns, Leighton "avoids recreating a period of [the] past ... instead he draws on ... the "best" epoch of ancient art to represent a universal Hellenism independent of specific time and place." Jenkyns, *Dignity and Decadence*, 212.

⁴⁵ Julian Freeman, *Life at Arm's Length: Sir Edward Poynter Bt, GCVO, PRA, 1836–1919: A Pupil at Brighton College from 1849–1850* (London: Brighton College, 1995), 6.

⁴⁶ Gaunt, *Victorian Olympus*, 46–48.

⁴⁷ Freeman, *Arm's Length*, 6.

⁴⁸ As Prettejohn showed, the archaeological accuracy of *The Catapult* was the very attribute that most impressed contemporary reviewers: "The critic for the *Daily Telegraph*, the morning paper

subject painting that “hovers ambiguously between the categories of history and genre, since their ‘heroes’ are anonymous common soldiers.”⁴⁹ Additionally, though the event in which the scene takes place is historical, the scene itself is unrecorded, thus falling outside of the traditional academic definition of “historical.”

The rise of British classical-genre painting coincided with the rise of the middle class and the wide dissemination of archaeological knowledge in popular publications. Further inspiration came from the first systematic excavations of Pompeii by the Italian government in 1861.⁵⁰ News of the rediscovery of great works of art reinforced the lofty ideals of classical aesthetics that had been revered in Britain since the eighteenth century. But other long-lost artefacts, everyday implements buried for centuries in their original contexts beneath layers of hardened ash, stimulated an antiquarian interest in the common life of the ancients. Furthermore, the poignant discovery of the remains of Vesuvius’s victims, their agonised forms preserved in ashen hollows, stirred a measure of empathy for the plight of the ordinary Roman. Together these discoveries lent an element of humanity to the past, invigorating the notion of the British people as the great inheritors of classical civilisation’s sweeping legacy.⁵¹

These types of revelations, coupled with the development of photography and its rapid addition to the painter’s arsenal, enabled painters such as Poynter and Alma-Tadema to achieve a previously unmatched degree of archaeological specificity.

with the largest circulation among the classes that Roger Fry disparaged as “half-educated,” stressed the “intimate technical knowledge of Roman siege operations” displayed in the picture, noting Vitruvius’s description of the catapult and the reliefs of Trajan’s column as possible sources. P.G. Hamerton, addressing the middle-class readership of the *Saturday Review*, was similarly enthusiastic, concluding that “this is historical painting of a rational and valuable kind.” Prettejohn, “Recreating Rome,” 66.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, 59.

⁵⁰ Jeremy Maas, *Victorian Painters* (1969; repr., London: Barrie and Jenkins, 1988), 177; Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 28.

⁵¹ Catharine Edwards, “The Roads to Rome,” in *Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century*, ed. Catharine Edwards and Michael Liversidge, (London: Merrell Holberton, 1996), 17.

Alma-Tadema had received his early training in the tradition of northern still-life painting, whose practitioners are noted for their meticulous method and finely-detailed work.⁵² Additionally, a visit to Rome and a tour of the ruins of Pompeii and Herculaneum in 1863 had impressed the artist deeply.⁵³ In the words of Jeremy Maas, Alma-Tadema resolved to employ his technical abilities “to paint scenes from classical antiquity, confining himself to social and military history and not, like Leighton, to the rarefied world of classical mythology.”⁵⁴

Alma-Tadema hoped to elevate art by grounding it in factual detail, not by lifting it to Leighton’s heroic heights. Alma-Tadema’s *Spring*, for example, depicts a Roman bacchanalian ritual. The pagan celebration, complete with antique musical instruments, ceremonial objects, and an attention to ancient fashion, coincided with the popularity of late-Victorian springtime celebrations. As Kestner observed: “The parallels drawn . . . between ancient customs and contemporary practices universalised individual experiences, providing continuity amid the disorientation of industrial transition.”⁵⁵

By contrast, Leighton’s paintings are considerably less pedestrian, approaching a realisation of philosopher Arthur Schopenhauer’s (1788–1860) conception of the “sublime.” The dream-like world and powerful beauty of *The Garden of the Hesperides* from 1892 (fig. 18), for example, might inspire the viewer to the contemplation of the “infinite greatness of the universe in space and time.”⁵⁶ For Leighton, superfluous detail in the vein of Alma-Tadema could only distract.

As art historian Louise Lippincott observed, “the extraordinary elaboration of paintings such as *Spring* developed from Alma-Tadema’s belief that when it came to

⁵² Edwards, “The Roads to Rome,” 17.

⁵³ Maas, *Victorian Painters*, 182.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ Kestner, *Mythology and Misogyny*, 18.

⁵⁶ Arthur Schopenhauer, *The World as Will and Idea: Abridged in One Volume*, Everyman’s Library Edition, ed. David Berman and trans. Jill Berman (London: J.M. Dent, 1995), 129.

beauty, more was more.”⁵⁷ Grounded in the minutiae of “insignificant objects,” Alma-Tadema’s work in this sense is comparable to Dutch still-life, a type of painting admired by Schopenhauer for its intricate beauty.⁵⁸ Although Schopenhauer believed that still-life paintings were less “sublime” than high art, they did afford the viewer a degree of “spiritual peace.”⁵⁹ Viewed in a similar light, Alma-Tadema’s archaeological concerns appear less inspiring than the sublime works of Leighton, but somewhat more substantial than the “trifles” scorned by Roger Fry.

The descent and devaluation of ancient Roman subject matter, traced by Jenkyns and described by Prettejohn, inevitably diluted Alma-Tadema’s achievement. Thus, Wood writes in *Olympian Dreamers* that the artist’s “intensity of ... vision was unfortunately lost on most of his followers.”⁶⁰ Whether Wood means to include Godward amongst these “painters of the patio” is uncertain, since the author compares him positively with Leighton. In any case, Wood believes these unnamed “second-rate” painters, which probably include Godward’s peers Bulleid and Ryland, “imitated” and “debased” Alma-Tadema’s style.⁶¹ Interestingly, Godward’s own “patio” pictures bear remarkable similarities to those of his friends. Godward’s *The Pergola* of 1898 (fig. 19), for instance, an untitled domestic scene by Bullied from 1911 (fig. 20), and the undated *Shy—Et Dona Ferentes* (fig. 21) by Ryland, all feature youthful female models, well-rendered marble, and attention to the details of ancient objects and fashion.

In summary, Leighton’s classical subjects in works such as *Perseus on Pegasus* continued the tradition of “history painting” as defined by Joshua Reynolds

⁵⁷ Louise Lippincott, *Lawrence Alma Tadema: Spring* (Malibu, CA: J. Paul Getty Museum, 1991), 73.

⁵⁸ Schopenhauer, *Will and Idea*, 120.

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*, 120–21.

⁶⁰ Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 29.

⁶¹ *Ibid.*

and descended from the Old Masters. These works were considered morally ennobling because they combine heroic and/or mythological subjects with an idealised, monumental style. Paintings such as Alma-Tadema's *Spring*, and many by Bulleid, Godward, and Ryland, depict scenes from daily life and are grounded in archaeological fact. These may be described as classical-genre because they deal with the "momentary and particular" in both subject and style.

This is not to imply that Leighton did not observe or copy nature or that Alma-Tadema never altered the facts of archaeology. In practice, the two camps often inter-mingled; no classical-subject painting belongs to one pure category. Thus, though Godward sometimes borrowed the ennobling forms of high art for paintings such as *A Fair Reflection*, he grounded his art in the archaeological specificity of classical genre.

Chapter 2

Archaeological Foundations and Moral Meaning

The fact remains that ... imitative painting may be so admirably done as to become of a high order or merit. ... Nevertheless, it is only the groundwork of ideal art, and is like the language in which the poet expresses his thoughts.

The most remarkable feature of Godward's *oeuvre* is its homogeneity. That he evolved at all in either subject or style is difficult to discern. Thus, Swanson describes the visible effects of an Italian tour, undertaken by the artist between 1905 and 1907, as "barely noticeable."¹ On the other hand, Godward's permanent move to Rome only four years later suggests that it did affect his soul. From 1912 on, a greater proportion of the artist's paintings contain landscape components and still-life arrangements of fresh fruit. Swanson assumes quite reasonably that Godward's interest in these elements reflects their ready availability in his new Mediterranean environment.² Still, the artist's focus remained unchanged: lovely classical women amidst antiquarian objects, as in *The Fruit Vendor* of 1917 (fig. 22).

Godward's lion in *The Fruit Vendor* and Poynter's in *Israel in Egypt* from 1867 (fig. 23) both look toward the viewer, paws crossed in the Egyptian style.³ There is no coincidence in their resemblance: every classical-subject painter in Victorian Britain would have been familiar with the Egyptian Sculpture Gallery at the British Museum and its famous pair of sculpted lions named for Lord Prudhoe (fig. 24).⁴ Poynter modelled his lion for *Israel in Egypt* after the Prudhoe from direct

¹ Swanson, *Godward*, 83.

² *Ibid.*, 100.

³ W. Stephenson Smith, *The Art and Architecture of Ancient Egypt*, ed. Nikolaus Pevsner, The Pelican History of Art (Harmondsworth, Middlesex, UK: Penguin Books, 1958), 153.

⁴ Ian Jenkins, *Archaeologists & Aesthetes in the Sculpture Galleries of the British Museum, 1800–1939* (London: British Museum Press, 1992), 30, 39.

observation.⁵ Godward lived in Rome when he painted *The Fruit Vendor*, inspired by the local Egyptian-style lions of Nektanebos I (380–363 BCE) (fig. 25).⁶

Nevertheless, Godward would have been familiar with *Israel in Egypt*, and the popularity of Poynter's lion based on the Prudhoe may have encouraged him to paint his own. By the same token, Godward's lion largely adheres to the truth of another artefact, and in this sense, it is two generations removed from the Prudhoe.

Neither Godward nor Poynter copied their models exactly. The demands of composition and format required both painters to adjust their lions' features for the sake of visual harmony. Neither is "carved" from its original material. Godward changed his from dark porphyry to serene white marble, and Poynter's is no longer composed of the Prudhoe's red granite. The *Art Journal*'s reviewer described Poynter's as "painted plaster or canvas" to contrast with its strong surroundings.⁷ Otherwise, Poynter has preserved and "restored" most of the details of the Prudhoe's pose and its hieroglyphic base.⁸ Godward, on the other hand, has omitted Nektanebos's hieroglyphs from his lion. Beyond physical changes, however, each lion relates differently to its environment. Where Godward's lion and his human figure balance each other, Poynter's lion has been made colossal. Although the two lions are similar in many ways, each is ill suited to the context of its cousin; it would be absurd to exchange them.

To varying degrees, both lions, like both paintings, are grounded in archaeological fact. Thus, where Poynter's *Israel in Egypt* and Godward's *The Fruit Vendor* appear to have little in common besides the central presence of Egyptian

⁵ Patrick Conner notes "crayon sketches by Poynter of one of the lions, together with figures which were to appear in *Israel in Egypt*, survive in the Museum's collection" and that Poynter "had lodgings opposite the Museum, and must have known the lion sculptures well." Patrick Conner, "Wedding Archaeology to Art: Poynter's *Israel in Egypt*," in *Influences in Victorian Art and Architecture*, ed. Sarah Macready and F.H. Thompson (London: Society of Antiquaries, 1985), 114.

⁶ Poynter would also have been familiar with the lions of Nektanebos I. *Ibid.*

⁷ *Art Journal* (1 June 1867), 139.

⁸ H.R. Hall, "Objects of Tut'ankhamūn in the British Museum," *The Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 14, No. ½ (June 1928): 76.

lions, both paintings can be described as classical genre. Indeed, the key to deciphering each painting's meaning is to determine the role of the lion within it. Did Godward and Poynter aspire to the level of high art by imbuing their lions with moral, didactic, or symbolic significance, or are the lions primarily amoral, decorative, and, therefore, Aesthetic?

Poynter's *Israel in Egypt* is an imaginary scene, illustrating a passage from Exodus that describes the brutal plight of the Israelites as they labour in captivity under the Pharaoh. Here, whipped and beaten by Egyptian overseers, slaves transport massive stone lions amidst a magnificent backdrop of temples.⁹ Poynter assembled this frieze-like composition from a range of material spread over 3,000 years of Egyptian history and many different sites.¹⁰ In restoring these monuments from ruins to a state of unspoiled splendour, the artist has rendered the details of hieroglyphs and architecture with painstaking attention to archaeological "accuracy." Still, Poynter's Pharaonic Egypt is a pastiche constructed for theatrical effect. As art historian Patrick Conner observes, the scene is "wilfully incorrect and historically false ... Poynter and every Victorian schoolboy would have known [that] a structure dating from the Christian era could have hardly appeared during the Israelites' captivity in Egypt."¹¹ Nevertheless, the idea of archaeological and historical accuracy, for the Victorian painter as well as his audience, remained quite flexible.¹²

More important was the painter's moral intent made manifest in his work. Thus, where the *Art Journal's* reviewer forgave *Israel in Egypt's* archaeological incongruities, he believed that Poynter, in choosing to depict the Israelites' suffering,

⁹ *Art Journal*, 139.

¹⁰ Poynter "built" his Egyptian city from an assortment of monuments and motifs taken from easily accessible printed sourcebooks. Conner, "Wedding Archaeology," 113–14.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 113.

¹² *Ibid.*, 114.

“labours under the disadvantage of ... a disagreeable ... [and] revolting subject.”¹³ Yet, *Israel in Egypt*'s archaeological aspect appealed to many of its original viewers, who felt it to be sufficiently didactic.¹⁴ Writer Briony Llewellyn credits the Victorian's interest in Pharaonic Egypt largely with its connection to moral lessons found in the Old Testament.¹⁵ Although Poynter used his Old Testament subject matter partially as a pretext to display his skill as a draughtsman and painter, he also used its narrative theme to instil his audience with a moral lesson. Indeed, *Israel in Egypt*'s vast horizontality resembles a procession of remote, impersonal actors scrolling across a stage set.

For narrative subjects such as this, painters needed to convey sequential action within the limitations of their two-dimensional canvas. Historian Martin Meisel describes the solution as analogous to a musical composition in which simultaneous but separate tonal phrases indicate movement: “Beginning with an assumed or ... ‘perceived’ coexistence of action and reaction, stimulus and response, the painter would represent contiguous events as ‘phrases’ of action, or moments with duration.”¹⁶ It may be inaccurate to apply Meisel's use of the word “phrase” to paintings such as *The Fruit Vendor*, which might instead be described as “phraseless.” Meisel's term “phrase” implies action, and action requires space and time, but the figures in Godward's painting appear immutable.

By contrast, Poynter's lion in *Israel in Egypt* represents the central phrase in a multi-phrase narrative, functioning as the axis for three symbolic sub-phrases embodied by three groups of figures around it. Clockwise from left to right are 1) a Greek-style

¹³ *Art Journal*, 139.

¹⁴ For the *Athenaeum*'s reviewer, *Israel in Egypt* was a “mine of archaeological knowledge.” Conner, “Wedding Archaeology,” 112.

¹⁵ Briony Llewellyn, “The Victorian Vision of Egypt,” in *The Inspiration of Egypt: Its Influence on British Artists, Travellers and Designers, 1700–1900*, ed. Patrick Conner (Brighton, UK: Brighton Borough Council, 1983), 117.

¹⁶ Martin Meisel, *Realizations: Narrative, Pictorial, and Theatrical Arts in Nineteenth-Century England* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1983), 20.

“heroic” nude with labourers, 2) a slave and overseer, and 3) a sympathetic woman and fallen slave.¹⁷ In this interpretation, Poynter’s lion is a symbol for Christ. Indeed, Poynter would have been familiar with the symbolic language of Christian iconography through the popular publications of Anna Jameson and other sources.¹⁸ Jameson’s engraved books and articles, first appearing in 1848, reveal the meaning of Christian symbolism in the art of Renaissance painters from Cimabue to Titian.¹⁹

In her best-known work, *Sacred and Legendary Art*, Jameson described one function of the lion in Christian art as a symbol of the Redeemer, “the Lion of the tribe of Judah.”²⁰ Thus interpreted in *Israel in Egypt*, Christ the Redeemer stands at the centre of an earthly cycle of virtue and vice embodied by the three figure groups: the heroic nude with labourers, purity and toil; the slave and overseer, bondage and oppression; the sympathetic woman and fallen slave, charity and redemption. According to Jameson, however, a lion might also symbolise the Redeemer’s Resurrection.²¹ In this case, an event from the Old Testament prefigures the New so that Poynter’s procession of Israelites corresponds with Christ’s approach to Calvary. The Israelites’ misery whilst straining under the weight of the lion parallels Christ’s suffering whilst carrying the Cross. The sympathetic woman and fallen slave are analogous to the Sixth Station where Veronica wipes Jesus’s face. As the Prudhoe lions served to guard the temple of Amenhotep III (1390–1352 BCE), so is Poynter’s lion a guardian of Christian morality.²² *Israel in Egypt*’s central lion is only one of

¹⁷ Poynter’s heroic nude is reminiscent of the famous *Discobolus*.

¹⁸ Anderson and Wright, *Heaven on Earth*, 22.

¹⁹ Reprints of Jameson’s books were sold through the second decade of the twentieth century. Judith Johnston, *Anna Jameson: Victorian, Feminist, Woman of Letters* (Aldershot, England: Scolar Press, 1997), 1, 157.

²⁰ Anna Jameson, *Sacred and Legendary Art*, 3d ed. (London: Longman, Brown, Green, Longmans, & Roberts, 1857), 1: 27–28.

²¹ *Ibid.*, 28.

²² The Prudhoe lions originally guarded the Temple of Soleb in Nubia before Amenhotep III appropriated them for his own temple. A Meroite ruler later moved them south to the city of Gebel

several identical figures in the painting destined to serve as Pharaoh's guardian, true to archaeological "fact."

With the lion in *The Fruit Vendor*, Godward has discarded any pretence of truth to archaeological context. The lion's material and its environment have both been Graeco-Romanised, completely disconnected from ancient Egypt. Indeed, unlike Poynter's lion, the Prudhoe, or the original Nektanebos, Godward's lion cannot be the guardian of any building. Had Godward meant his terrace to represent the approach to an ancient monument, *The Fruit Vendor's* lion would be backward, gazing into the structure instead of looking out. Beyond this, Godward's lion lacks the magical power of the Pharaoh's cartouche and other hieroglyphs. Still, its commanding position at the edge of a terrace and its relation to the human figure does suggest guardianship.

Godward's lion, like Poynter's, might also represent the Redeemer at the centre of a moral allegory. The still-life element of the fruit could be merely decorative, or it may be allusive. Godward's female fruit vendor may be a stand-in for the more traditional flower girl, commonly understood to connote prostitution. The Victorians and Edwardians were quite familiar with the age-old question: "You with the roses, rosy is your charm; but what do you sell, yourself or the roses, or both?"²³ Although Godward substituted fruit for flowers, the insinuation of impropriety would have been clear to his contemporaries.

If Godward's lion is interpreted as the Redeemer, this reading becomes embedded with moral and didactic significance: the fallen woman, resting her head at Christ's right side (who himself sits at God's right hand), seeks forgiveness.

Analogous to the story of the adulteress in the Book of John (8:1–8:11), the Redeemer

Barkal. British Museum, "Red Granite Lion of Amenhotep III," <http://www.thebritishmuseum.ac.uk/compass/obj22.html> (accessed May 14, 2007).

²³ Elizabeth Prettejohn, "Catalogue II: Recreating Rome," in *Imagining Rome: British Artists and Rome in the Nineteenth Century*, ed. Catharine Edwards and Michael Liversidge (London: Merrell Holberton, 1996), 132.

first protects and then pardons her. Christ's admonishment, "he that is without sin among you, let him cast the first stone" applies to the viewer who passes judgment on the subject. Godward's lion has become the guardian of the fruit vendor's dignity.

The fresh fruit itself could carry moral significance. Jameson observed:

The apple was the received emblem of the Fall of Man and original sin. Placed in pictures of the Madonna and Child, either in the hand of the Infant Christ, or presented by an angel, it signified Redemption from the consequences of the Fall. The pomegranate bursting open, and the seeds visible, was an emblem of the future—of hope in immortality [i.e., the Resurrection].²⁴

Imagining that Godward substituted peaches for apples and an open melon for the open pomegranate, the lion-as-Redeemer might then represent the Child, and the woman Mary. The humble wooden table could serve as the hand of the Infant Christ or as a stand-in for the angel. Here, Godward's lion has become the guardian of Christian hope. Whether the lion represents the Redeemer or the Resurrection, both would be analogous to the role of Poynter's lion. Considering the moralising tone of Victorian society and the character of his early artistic influences, these Christian interpretations of *The Fruit Vendor* are plausible.

Indeed, Godward's mother was a strict, God-fearing woman who strongly disapproved of his art. Swanson believes that the painter possessed a "repressed personality," a "tormented soul," and, particularly in his later years, a "broken spirit."²⁵ Moreover, the author describes Godward's move to Rome as an "escape" from harsh moral criticism.²⁶

English professor Kate Flint observes that British art critics as late as 1910 were "often vehemently moralistic, dealing quite freely in adjectives like 'noble' and

²⁴ Jameson, *Sacred and Legendary*, 35.

²⁵ Swanson, *Godward*, 131.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 93.

‘exalted’ or ‘base,’ ‘vile,’ ‘corrupt,’ ‘sordid’ and ‘vicious.’”²⁷ Although Godward painted *The Fruit Vendor* in Rome in 1917, it may contain the ghosts of Victorian and Edwardian moral expectations. Indeed, Alma-Tadema had sometimes couched his art in moral terms by inscribing didactic messages onto the frames of his paintings.

The Coliseum from 1896 (fig. 26), for instance, offers clear evidence of Alma-Tadema’s moral convictions. This imaginary scene, witnessed from the perspective of three female figures, depicts the aftermath of an important gladiatorial contest during an unchronicled moment in the history of ancient Rome.²⁸ Although the artist has restored to pristine condition Western civilisation’s most infamous edifice at its bloody and glorious height, the figures provide an element of human interest; they are the foremost phrase in a multi-phrase composition. Additionally, Alma-Tadema included an inscription from Byron’s *Childe Harold’s Pilgrimage* on the frame:

And here the buzz of eager nations ran
 In murmur’d pity of loud-roared applause
 As man was slaughtered by his fellow man,
 Wherefore slaughtered? Wherefore, but because
 Such were the bloody circus’ genial laws,
 The Imperial pleasure, Wherefore not?
 What matters where we fall to fill the maws
 Of worms—on battle plains or listed spot?
 Both are but theatres where the chief actors rot.²⁹

As the inscription suggests, Alma-Tadema viewed *The Coliseum* as a moral vehicle, a means by which he might remind his audience of the highest aspirations of their nobler nature. With the express purpose of achieving this end, the artist has placed his trio of painted spectators—along with his actual audience—high above the

²⁷ Kate Flint, “Moral Judgement and the Language of English Art Criticism, 1870–1910,” *Oxford Art Journal* 6, No. 2 (1983): 59.

²⁸ The female figures on the balcony include a mother and her two young daughters; one is an adolescent, the other a prepubescent girl. *Athenaeum* (2 May 1896), 587; Vern Grosvenor Swanson, *The Biography and Catalogue Raisonné of the Paintings of Sir Lawrence Alma-Tadema* (London: Garton, 1990), 254.

²⁹ Excerpt from *Childe Harold’s Pilgrimage: A Romaunt. Canto IV* by George Gordon, Lord Byron (1788–1824), first published in 1818. *Ibid.*

coarseness and cruelty of the mob and sufficiently removed from the whims of the Imperial will.

Alma-Tadema hoped his bourgeois audience would imagine themselves perched upon the parapet high above the crowd, and that they might identify with the mixed emotions of curiosity and wonder expressed by the figures.³⁰ Indeed, Alma-Tadema's lofty trio represents a moral alternative to "Imperial pleasure;" they perform a mediating function, rendering comprehensible the artist's didactic inscription. One of the figures wears a silver diadem to indicate her Hellenic origin, reflecting the Victorian bias toward the "superior" morality of the ancient Greek intellect. "It is easy to imagine," wrote a reviewer in the *Athenaeum*, "that in her nobler spirit some thought of the [Coliseum's] victims ... arose."³¹ In Alma-Tadema's *The Coliseum*, the decadent grandeur of Imperial Rome is offset by the transcendental beauty and implied morality of ancient Greece.

Alma-Tadema painted a similar feminine trio in *A Coign of Vantage* from 1895 (fig. 27). High upon a terrace overlooking a sun-drenched Mediterranean, classical maidens peer anxiously out to sea. Far below, two ships carry their male lovers home from distant lands. *A Coign of Vantage* illustrates Alma-Tadema's theme of "waiting women" who depend upon men for physical and emotional support.³² In *The Coliseum*, the artist's inscription had anachronistically connected the Grecian woman to a Christian consciousness abhorrent to the cruelties of the arena. Here, the simple concern of all three women is the speedy return of their male lovers.

A fourth figure in *A Coign of Vantage* appears as an Egyptian-style lion similar to those of Godward and Poynter. In the same manner as theirs, Alma-

³⁰ Asleson, "Academics and Classicists," 190.

³¹ *Athenaeum*, 587.

³² Kestner, *Mythology and Misogyny*, 279.

Tadema's lion is a watchful sentinel and loyal protector.³³ In this painting, however, the lion-artefact has become nearly indistinguishable from a "living" figure. It does not guard the women, but seems instead to merge with the figures as an extension of their collective psyche. Similarly, in *The Coliseum*, Alma-Tadema has "merged" his human figures with a life-size bronze nude. Although watchful like the lion, it holds an unguarded and vulnerable pose as it strokes its hair in a seductive gesture indicating sexual availability. The statue's hairstyle also echoes that worn by the dark-haired girl who monopolises the balcony's best view. Indeed, the statue is the only figure on the parapet who looks directly toward the Coliseum, the consular procession near its base, and all they represent: wealth, power, blood, and sex. Perhaps the statue expresses the latent desires trapped within the repressed psyche of its living counterpart, acknowledging the woman's lust for those worldly gratifications she might only obtain through her dependence upon men.

Kestner theorises that paintings such as these "strongly enforce" Alma-Tadema's belief in the mental inferiority of women. This idea is linked to the chronic and sometimes severe mental instability of the artist's wife and daughter, who often appeared as characters in his scenes. "To counteract [their] madness," Kestner wrote, "[Alma-Tadema] portrayed women's conventional role as passive lover or satisfied mother," suggesting sexual dependence.³⁴ If true, Alma-Tadema's thinking would only mirror the commonly-held Victorian belief that women's "fragile" psychology was a symptom of their physical delicacy relative to men. This conception seems to support the thrust of Kestner's thesis: that Alma-Tadema, Godward, and the rest of British classical-subject painters were misogynists—literally, woman-haters.

³³ "Frédéric Bastet has identified the bronze animal as a free copy of an Egyptian sphinx from the Villa San Michele at Capri (the home of Swedish writer and physician, Axel Munthe, built in 1890 on the site of an ancient Roman house)." Rosemary Barrow et al., *Sir Lawrence Alma-Tadema*, ed. Edwin Becker et al. (Liverpool, UK: Walker Art Gallery, 1997), 256.

³⁴ Kestner, *Mythology and Misogyny*, 279.

Art historian Lynda Nead, however, notes the link between female dependency and the twentieth-century notion of misogyny was foreign to the Victorian mind:

The condition of dependency was believed to be a natural and gratifying component of respectable femininity. Middle-class morality proposed that men should treat women with decorum, respect and propriety; ... Male veneration, it was claimed, upheld the delicacy and purity of women and, far from oppressing them, elevated them to a superior position.³⁵

For Alma-Tadema, the classical female figure became the ideal(ised) transmitter of Victorian middle-class values. Ladies in paintings such as *The Coliseum* and *A Coign of Vantage* broadcast moral messages like radio towers from lofty heights. Moreover, if the classical female transmitted morality, the artefacts amongst her amplified her signal. Elizabeth Prettejohn recognised that “part of the fascination of ... [classical] genre scenes, for their original audiences, was that they ‘filled the holes’ in the ... material environment with impersonations of the lost human inhabitants.”³⁶

Alma-Tadema’s didactic messages may be inscribed or implied, but for his original audience, these classical females served as moral mirrors. The inclusion of Byron’s verse on *The Coliseum*’s frame, warning against the evils of unchecked power and the brutal consequences of “Imperial pleasure,” offered a noble example to which they could aspire.³⁷ In attempting to achieve what Kestner calls the “universalisation” of experience, Alma-Tadema merged his human figures with

³⁵ “The idea of dependency as a sign of femininity was ... ratified within medical discourse.” Lynda Nead, *Myths of Sexuality: Representations of Women in Victorian Britain* (Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1988), 29.

³⁶ Prettejohn, “Recreating Rome,” 68.

³⁷ Prettejohn observes that paintings such as *The Coliseum* “apparently [use] historical representations as a straightforward affirmation of imperialist ideology. ... [But they] seem to contradict and undermine that project by calling attention to the disreputable aspects of the same Roman spectacle.” Elizabeth Prettejohn, “Lawrence Alma-Tadema and the Modern City of Ancient Rome,” *Art Bulletin* 84, No. 1 (March 2002): 120.

figure-artefacts to conflate the present and the past in the contemplation of eternal moral truths.³⁸

Godward often borrowed Alma-Tadema's waiting-woman theme. Unlike *The Coliseum* and *A Coign of Vantage*, however, which exemplify Alma-Tadema's habit of grouping female figures in scenes with multiple phrases, Godward's waiting women tend toward single-figure, phraseless compositions containing little archaeological detail. Early exceptions are *Expectation* from around 1887 (fig. 28) and *Sewing Girl* from 1889 (fig. 29). Only *Sewing Girl*'s upper right-hand corner, where a youthful maiden looks longingly out to sea, truly fits the waiting-woman formula. Godward has committed the majority of his canvas to an abundantly detailed scene of contented domesticity. In Godward's *Expectation*, the woman reacts anxiously to the sight of approaching ships, recalling similar action in *A Coign of Vantage*. These two paintings along with *Sewing Girl* may therefore be interpreted as reinforcing Victorian "domestic ideology" emphasising women's "naturally" dependent role in middle-class society.³⁹

Additionally, Godward embedded both *Expectation* and *Sewing Girl* with symbolic objects. The ideas these objects represent vary according to their locations in space and time, so an accurate reading of their meanings is a function of archaeologically-specific detail. A prominent feature of *Expectation* is a bas-relief of Cupid carrying a bow and reaching for an arrow from his quiver. That the carving depicts the figure of a little boy and not a full-grown youth confirms that this is in fact the Roman Cupid and not his counterpart, the Grecian Eros. Moreover, Cupid's downward gaze is directed toward a lizard crawling at his feet, providing yet another

³⁸ Kestner, *Mythology and Misogyny*, 18.

³⁹ Smith uses the term "domestic ideology" to describe the Victorians' manner of thinking about women's roles. Alison Smith, *The Victorian Nude: Sexuality, Morality and Art* (Manchester, UK: Manchester University Press, 1996), 133.

clue to the carving's Roman origin. In the Roman world, the lizard was a symbol of death and rebirth.⁴⁰

As Swanson observes, the Roman Cupid, as the god of purely sensual love, alludes to the maiden's "rendezvous with her lover."⁴¹ Yet, the presence of Cupid's lizard, whose death and rebirth make it immortal, along with the passage of time indicated by the setting of the Mediterranean sun, suggest a deeper meaning. Perhaps Cupid, the lizard, and cyclical time together recall the ennobling story of Eros, the Greek god of love from which the Roman Cupid derives. As Eros brought order from chaos during the formation of the world through the uniting power of love, so did "natural" constructions of gender bring moral order to Victorian society. Alma-Tadema's Hellenic woman in *The Coliseum* offers a moral alternative to Rome's Imperial decadence; in Godward's *Expectation*, the "superior" morality of Grecian Eros is greater than Roman Cupid's sensual ardour.

The meaning of a pair of white doves in Godward's *Sewing Girl* also depends upon the specifics of archaeologically. An airborne dove is silhouetted against the sky above the stairway, whilst another has alighted amongst several pigeons. The bronze mask of Zeus, Triton's conch shell, marble acroteria in bas-relief, and a terra cotta vessel inscribed with Hellenic patterns are evidence that the scene's intended location is ancient Greece. Perhaps Godward felt compelled by conscience to "redeem" his pagan picture with the inclusion of Christian symbology. Here, perhaps, one dove represents peace and the other the Holy Ghost.

The dove is also an attribute of Aphrodite, the Greek goddess of love and beauty. Aphrodite ruled over fertility, generation, and marriage, and was often

⁴⁰ Miranda Bruce-Mitford, *The Illustrated Book of Signs and Symbols* (London: Dorling Kindersley, 1996), 58.

⁴¹ Swanson, *Godward*, 172.

worshipped for her power over the sea and seafaring.⁴² Indeed, the pagan dove is more appropriate than the Christian dove to *Sewing Girl*'s subject. Godward's doves in *Sewing Girl*, like Cupid, the lizard, and time's passage in *Expectation*, may reflect Victorian values by denoting social order.

Could the dove-in-flight be symbolic of the waiting maiden, her youthful beauty, the soaring of sexual desire, or the return of her sweetheart from the sea? If so, the earthbound dove would correspond to *Sewing Girl*'s foreground figure who, in performing her household chore, symbolises women's "proper" role in Victorian society as wife, mother, and daughter. As such, she represents a feminine archetype corresponding to Aphrodite's domestic aspect as the personification of marriage, children, and family. The waiting maiden in the background is an archetype of dependent love and beauty, representing the sensual aspect of Victorian femininity. In *The Coliseum* and *A Coign of Vantage* by Alma-Tadema, and *Expectation* and *Sewing Girl* by Godward, archaeology and morality are inextricably linked.

Godward's *Absence Makes the Heart Grow Fonder* (fig. 30), painted nearly a quarter of a century after *Expectation* and *Sewing Girl*, also borrowed Alma-Tadema's waiting-woman theme. This phraseless painting, featuring a woman with a Japanese fan, shows a strong Aesthetic influence. Despite the sentimentality of its title, *Absence Makes the Heart Grow Fonder* is characterised by the absence of action. The woman within is inert and expressionless, even as a distant ship at upper left, presumably carrying her male lover, floats motionless upon a tranquil sea.

The ships in *A Coign of Vantage* move rapidly toward the shore, as the direction and froth of their wakes clearly indicate. In *Absence Makes the Heart Grow Fonder*, however, time and space appear suspended; whether the woman mourns her

⁴² N.G.L. Hammond and H.H. Scullard, eds., *The Oxford Classical Dictionary*, 2nd ed. (1970; repr., Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 1989), 80.

lover's departure or thoughtfully awaits his return is uncertain; both evidence of action and archaeological clues are lacking. Without phrases indicating action, or the archaeological specificity of artefacts such as bronze figures or marble carvings, the woman-as-object, the blank slate of Aestheticism, and the classical beauty are seemingly all that remain. Godward's painting contains no didactic message, and all traces of moral meaning have disappeared.

As Godward moved gradually toward a more Aesthetic mode of composition, the balance of his work became figure-centred after around 1905. His early multi-phrase paintings such as *Expectation* and *Sewing Girl* are similar to Alma-Tadema's in that the human figures within them are subordinate to their antiquarian environment. In 1913's *The Belvedere* (fig. 31), however, another of Godward's paintings based upon the waiting-woman formula, the figure occupies a greater proportion of the image area than in single-figure works by Alma-Tadema from any date. In Alma-Tadema's *Resting* of 1882 (fig. 32), for instance, the human subject serves primarily to fill the archaeological hole.

The Fruit Vendor is one of Godward's most unusual compositions: why does the non-human figure appear equally important as the human one? Here, Godward has not attempted to "universalise" experience by Alma-Tadema's illusionistic method of merging the artefact with the human figures; each remains distinctly individual. Unlike Alma-Tadema's bronze figures in *The Coliseum* and *A Coign of Vantage*, Godward's lion neither extends nor reflects the woman's psyche, but seems instead to be a companion. Neither is the lion like Poynter's heavenly Redeemer in *Israel in Egypt*; here it appears domesticated.

Godward's lion may be the guardian of feminine beauty, whilst the woman embodies an amoral archetype of beauty, a thing-in-itself whose virtue resides in her

very existence as form and colour.⁴³ Indeed, neither her beauty nor her (in)action seem to function as moral mirrors. It remains to be seen whether or not she is truly the meaningless subject of an Aesthetic experiment, as Asleson describes the female figures of Moore.

⁴³ Smith, *Victorian Nude*, 185.

Chapter 3

Aestheticism, Amoralism, and Archetypes

While we respect these time-consecrated images and types, we do not allow them to fetter us, but trust in the progressive spirit of Christianity to furnish us with new impersonations of the good—new combinations of the beautiful.

— Anna Jameson, *Sacred and Legendary Art*, 1857

Many of Godward's paintings, not just those with waiting-women themes or large figure-artefacts, exhibit Aestheticism's amoral and decorative tendency.

A comparison of Godward's *The Mirror* of 1899 (fig. 33) to Moore's *A Wardrobe* of 1867 (fig. 34), for instance, reveals several similarities. From the point of view of the Victorian middle-class male, each offers a peek into the mysterious, private world of beautiful women: Moore's figure is (un)dressing whilst Godward's is grooming her hair. Similarities are also apparent in the figures' poses, their scale in relation to the dimensions of the canvas, their relation to the background and the proportions and compartmentalisation of the background elements. Since both artists have objectified their figures, neither has named his painting for its human subject, but for one of the ordinary objects found within the woman's intimate space.

Despite these resemblances, a closer examination reveals a basic disjunction: in *The Mirror* and *A Wardrobe*, Godward and Moore have objectified their female figures in fundamentally different ways. Moore's woman in *A Wardrobe* has been partially dehumanised. She strikes an unnatural, petrified pose resembling the idealised form of a Greek statue. Her half-marble, half-flesh colouring, mask-like visage and the stony hardness of her contours have resulted in a kind of "fossilised beauty."¹ The figure in Godward's *The Mirror* also exhibits a classical bearing, but her pose is more natural,

¹ Edwin Becker used the term "fossilised beauty" to characterise the female figures of Alma-Tadema. Edwin Becker, "The Soul of Things: Alma-Tadema and Symbolism," in *Sir Lawrence Alma-Tadema*, ed. Edwin Becker et al. (Liverpool, UK: Walker Art Gallery, 1997), 81.

and her soft, realistically-coloured flesh appears emphatically alive against the cold white marble wall. Where Moore has minimised his figure's sexual allure with a defeminising combination of diminutive breasts, broad shoulders, and powerful arms, Godward's woman is voluptuous. Moreover, both artists have used classical poses, settings, and objects to depersonalise their women by "removing" them far from the viewer in time and space.

Moore has reinforced his figure's role as a "convenient studio prop" by averting her gaze.² As one writer observed, "humanity ceased to interest [Moore] except as ... [an] arrangement of lines and masses ... [and for] its decorative appropriateness."³ Although Godward's woman also averts her eyes, her gaze is demure and coquettish. Swanson's description of another of Godward's paintings applies equally well to this one: "Fulsome breasts are clearly revealed through the diaphanous dress," he wrote, "adding an innocent sensualness to an otherwise tender moment from antiquity."⁴ Thus, where Moore's female figure in *A Wardrobe* has been formally objectified, Godward's objectification of his woman in *The Mirror* is not simply decorative, but primarily psychosexual.

The diaphanously-draped *Ionian Dancing Girl* of 1902 (fig. 35) exemplifies what Swanson called Godward's "genius for titillation." To present-day viewers, this sensual aspect of Godward's work may provoke a range of responses; for its original, middle-class male buyer, much of the painting's appeal can be safely ascribed to the dancing girl's sexual allure.⁵ Still, there was more to "beauties painting" than eroticism. The category had arisen as an offshoot of Victorian middle-class values promoting the male veneration of women. Thus, Godward's classical beauties were

² Asleson, *Moore*, 129.

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ Swanson, *Godward*, 86.

⁵ Swanson compares beauties painting to pin-up photography. *Ibid.*, 135.

an outgrowth of the beauties category in general, which had become popular in Europe during the nineteenth century across several styles of painting.⁶

Art historian Alison Smith believes that the Victorians' critical framework for observing the female figure "was loosely based on the Platonic concept of ideal beauty."⁷ For Godward as well, the contemplation of comely, unblemished womanhood might have been more than simply carnal; it may also have nurtured his soul. Swanson believes that Godward's maidens "often engage the spectator's consciousness through tender glances creating a psychological transcendentalism."⁸ Although many of Godward's works are alluring displays of external beauty, they also hint at a compelling but understated psychology residing within.

This does not mean to suggest that Godward came to ignore archaeological accuracy—as shown by the details of *The Fruit Vendor's* lion or the intricate ivory inlay on *Ionian Dancing Girl's* tambourine, quite the opposite is true. Indeed, Godward's classical beauties struck a delicate balance of sameness and variety that largely depended on the careful arrangement of objects.⁹ Swanson has likened the artist's tedious working method to still-life painting, believing that *Ionian Dancing Girl* "showcases Godward's abilities in all the areas for which he was most noted, including draperies, flesh, marble, floral, and Mediterranean landscape."¹⁰ According to Prettejohn, these details were "valued precisely for the technical skill involved in their representation."¹¹ In this sense, Godward was shrewdly commercial; his paintings were both conducive to speedy production *and* highly marketable. "Critics, collectors, and audiences," wrote Prettejohn, "continued to delight in archaeologically

⁶ Swanson, *Godward*, 135.

⁷ Smith, *Victorian Nude*, 186.

⁸ Swanson, *Godward*, 135

⁹ Prettejohn, "Recreating Rome," 67.

¹⁰ Swanson, *Godward*, 140; Prettejohn, "Catalogue II: Rome," 208.

¹¹ Prettejohn, "Recreating Rome," 67.

specific ... [ancient] objects” well into the twentieth century.¹² For Godward, however, archaeological objects became ancillary to feminine beauty.

Indeed, Godward’s primary concern was the exhaustive representation of the idealised female form. For a pure form to remain pure, however, it must be removed from corrupting influences. It must be self-sustaining and self-contained. According to Swanson, Godward desired to place his women within an “Elysian or halcyon ... ‘make-believe’ world.”¹³ Thus, Godward’s female figures typically inhabit a kind of display window, visually appealing yet physically inaccessible and psychologically incorruptible. By contrast, Alma-Tadema’s ladies often inhabit multi-phrase compositions containing portals or doorways, as in *The Frigidarium* of 1890 (fig. 36).

This depiction of daily life at a Roman bath contains two phrases. An aristocratic lady with her servants is the foremost phrase. The male servant draws aside a curtain to reveal another, more alluring phrase for which the lady is really a pretext. Indeed, Alma-Tadema’s open curtain is his invitation for his audience to “enter” the scene. Although the artist has provided his viewers with an apparently virtuous lady with whom they might linger for a moment, the way remains open to the pleasures of the bath. Godward’s phraseless *At the Thermae* from 1909 (fig. 37), however, illustrates the basic difference in his intent: here, the female figure is central. In pose, she resembles Alma-Tadema’s aristocratic lady, yet she exhibits a languor similar to the bather at the frigidarium’s entrance. Godward might have plucked her from behind Alma-Tadema’s curtain.

Godward has removed his figure in *At the Thermae* from a specific context; aside from the title and vague classical setting, he has dispensed with any Alma-Tadema-style pretext of decorum. Although Godward’s woman is tantalising, there is

¹² Prettejohn, “Recreating Rome,” 67.

¹³ Swanson, *Godward*, 135

only foreground, making it impossible for the viewer to “enter” as in Alma-Tadema’s scene. Moreover, Godward has suspended his figure in space and time; she functions essentially as a two-dimensional Hellenic statue, and the painted canvas is her niche. Aloof from any “physical” involvement with the viewer that might destroy her psychological significance, she remains undisturbed from without. Indeed, the position of the figure’s right arm in *At the Thermae* suggests action—is she dressing or disrobing?—but this only heightens the sense of eternal suspension.

The lady’s pose in *The Frigidarium* is equally ambiguous and evokes a similar feeling of timelessness. Nevertheless, she exists within a “three-dimensional” space wherein phrases can be defined by potential or completed action. To facilitate movement, Alma-Tadema’s foreground, middle ground, and background each open onto the other so that action may unfold in time.

Godward’s earliest multi-phrase works, those that are most derivative of Alma-Tadema, contain similar portals. It has been seen that the women in paintings such as *Expectation* and *Sewing Girl* are subordinate to their surroundings in the physical sense that they seem to fill archaeological holes. They are also psychologically subordinate in the sense that they are often compelled to interact with other figures, sometimes including children and men. Godward’s *Innocent Amusements* of 1891 (fig. 38), for instance, contains three phrases. In the foreground, a lady interrupts her sewing to balance a peacock feather on her fingertip; in the middle ground, a pair of young girls looks on; in the background, two patricians discuss affairs.¹⁴ In 1893’s *Yes or No?* (fig. 39), the woman’s male suitor woos her from behind an arched opening in a marble wall.¹⁵

As Godward’s paintings became increasingly centred on the lone female

¹⁴ Swanson, *Godward*, 181.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 188.

figure, Alma-Tadema-style portals largely disappear from his work—along with any human companions who might have filled them. From around 1905 on, few of Godward’s women remain physically engaged with more than comparatively minor objects such as flowers or pets. As in *At the Thermae*, however, most appear psychologically disengaged from their surroundings. As the artist liberated his women from their need for physical involvement with complex socio-material environments, he released them metaphorically from the moral demands of late-Victorian society. Thus, whilst many of Godward’s women only coyly titillate the viewer, several exhibit intimations of full sexual abandon.

A Priestess of Bacchus, painted in 1890 (fig. 40), is one of Godward’s earliest depictions of a “loose” woman. Here, an indolent maiden lounges on a marble exedra, recalling similarly-posed figures in works by Alma-Tadema such as *Resting*.¹⁶ The maiden in Godward’s multi-figure composition, however, wears an ivy wreath and holds a thyrsus, objects that identify her as a bacchante. Bacchantes were female worshippers of the Roman wine-god Bacchus infamous for their enthusiastic participation in rites of drunken and promiscuous revelry; the ivy and the phallic thyrsus, its long shaft topped with a seed-filled pinecone, are symbols of fertility. Could the presence of respectable citizens have inspired this bacchante to exchange depraved desires for virtuous hopes? If, as Swanson believes, she is “daydreaming about having a suitor like the couple descending the marble stairway,” what does it mean that she gazes directly, seductively, toward the viewer?¹⁷

Although Godward would have been familiar with the appearance of bacchantes and other classical types from engravings in Thomas Hope’s *Costume of the Ancients* and other printed sources, the figures in these drawings rarely meet the

¹⁶ An exedra is a Roman-style curved marble bench.

¹⁷ Swanson, *Godward*, 179.

viewer's gaze (fig. 41).¹⁸ Neither does a similar female type in Alma-Tadema's *A Bacchante* ("There he is!") of 1875 (fig. 42), who peers from a window at a bacchanalian celebration occurring out of the viewer's sight in the streets below. Here, Alma-Tadema has attempted to subvert her licentiousness. He insisted that the figure, despite her ivy, leopard skin, and thyrsus, "is not a bacchante but a [respectable] young Roman lady" eager to join her lover in the festivities.¹⁹ Only the painting's most educated viewers would have recognised the portion of marble relief on the wall depicting Apollo and the Three Graces, and understood its less-respectable meaning as a scene of seduction.²⁰ Alma-Tadema's figure in this painting is a dependent, waiting woman in bacchantic guise.

Godward's indolent bacchante in *A Priestess of Bacchus* bears a closer relation to the exhausted nude maenad (a Hellenic bacchante) in *The Altar of Dionysus* of 1886–88 by the Austrian Symbolist painter Gustav Klimt (1862–1918) (fig. 43). Much of Klimt's work from this period, with its classical subject matter, archaeological references, unconventional compositional style, hidden suggestions, and symbolic meaning, shows the strong influence of Alma-Tadema.²¹ Klimt's Grecian maenad, like Godward's Roman bacchante, appears sexually uninhibited. Unlike Alma-Tadema, neither Godward nor Klimt has subverted his figure's erotic suggestion; both women are unashamed to meet the viewer's eyes.

Although Alma-Tadema influenced both artists, the faces of his own figures betray little emotional depth, whilst those of Klimt and Godward hint at a more complex inner psyche. Indeed, art historian Edwin Becker believes that Klimt's figures

¹⁸ Hope's stated aim in compiling this work was "to afford artists a convenient and a cheap collection of those leading features of ancient costume of which the knowledge can least be dispensed with." Thomas Hope, *Costume of the Ancients*, new ed. (New York: Henry G. Bohn, 1841), 1:ix.

¹⁹ Barrow et al., *Alma-Tadema*, 191.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 191–92.

²¹ Becker, "Soul of Things," 79.

reflect a dichotomy between the so-called Apollonian and Dionysian, two “mutually opposing aesthetic impulses” described by the philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche (1844–1900) in 1872.²² As Becker explains, “the Apollonian [is] characterised by order and self-control, and the Dionysiac [*sic*] ... by wild, unbridled ecstasy.”²³ This is not to suggest that Godward was influenced by the Austrian artist’s work; if Godward was aware of Klimt at all, it may not have been until after 1900, and even then almost certainly through the latter’s highly-stylised figures. Nonetheless, many of Godward’s women display these same Apollonian or Dionysian characteristics.

Godward’s figure in *A Priestess of Bacchus*, for instance, along with his bacchante in *At the Gate of the Temple* of 1898 (fig. 44), might be considered Dionysian. Although the artist has not pictured them engaging in wanton acts, their prurient personas and unabashed gazes give them away. Indeed, both scenes are “reflective” according to the prevailing Victorian fashion of either foreshadowing an event or showing its consequences.²⁴ Thus, Waterhouse depicted his classical enchantress in 1896’s *Pandora* (fig. 45) a moment after indulging her curiosity by lifting the lid of her divine coffer. A wisp of smoke seen issuing from within signifies the release of its evil contents, but before their diffusion into the world. Waterhouse has conceived his *jeune fille fatale* as a nubile beauty, seemingly ensnared by otherworldly forces beyond her power to control.²⁵

Godward’s nude priestess in *The Delphic Oracle* of 1899 (fig. 46) is a similar type of *jeune fille fatale*. Here, the Pythoness is pictured sitting atop an altar as she

²² Becker, “Soul of Things,” 81.

²³ *Ibid*; Philosophy professor Aaron Ridley explains that the “intoxicated” Dionysian state represents the revelation of the “(alleged) truth” at the heart of the individual self, which is supposedly an illusion. The “dream-like” Apollonian state shields the individual from the full, devastating knowledge of that truth. For a further elucidation of Nietzsche’s concept, see Aaron Ridley, *Nietzsche on Art*, ed. Tim Crane and Jonathan Wolff, Routledge Philosophy Guidebook (London: Routledge, 2007), 13–21.

²⁴ Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 232, 236.

²⁵ Waterhouse’s classical enchantresses “cannot help themselves; it is the gods that have ordered things so. Passively, sadly, they are resigned to their fate.” Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 232, 236.

awaits the viewer's enquiry, mere moments before she inhales the mystical vapours that will send her into delirium. According to a contemporary description, "[her] deep, straight gaze suggests the inexplicable and inexpressive workings of divine control on human destiny."²⁶ Thus, Godward's Dionysian archetype may have tempted the middle-class male viewer to abandon himself to the repressed impulses of psychosexual desire.

Although many of Godward's titillating beauties gaze at the viewer directly, others, as in *The Mirror*, avert their eyes; either way, most appear drowsy, as if weary of the classical pretence. Godward's drowsy women in non-specific classical settings recall the remote, dreamy world of Leighton. From the 1870s on, Leighton populated many of his better-known paintings, both multi- and single-figure compositions, with languorous female types.²⁷ Godward's *A Siesta* of 1895 (fig. 47) was inspired by Leighton's *Flaming June* painted earlier the same year (fig. 48).²⁸ Swanson believes that comparisons of Godward to Leighton, like comparisons of Godward to Alma-Tadema, have limits:

[Godward] did not attempt to paint in the "grand manner" of Leighton's "high art." Though he was more formally classic than most painters of his day he eschewed the great themes of classicism. Rather his work pursued a strain of the "touch of languor" or *dolce far niente* trend of indolent ladies common in his day.²⁹

Godward entitled seven paintings *Dolce Far Niente*, but the one shown earlier from 1904 (see fig. 5) is also reminiscent of *Flaming June*. Swanson believes that the

²⁶ Swanson, *Godward*, 199.

²⁷ Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 54; Jenkyns observes that the "lights and colours of the south, so important to other classical painters of the period, seem not to have interested him at all." Even so, Leighton's heavy use of warm tones in these two pictures do suggest a warmer climate. Jenkyns, *Dignity and Decadence*, 212.

²⁸ By coincidence, Leighton's *Flaming June* and Godward's *A Siesta* both reside at the Museo de Arte de Ponce, Puerto Rico. Swanson, *Godward*, 55.

²⁹ Swanson, *Godward*, 134.

figure in this painting represents a physically spent maenad.³⁰ Although here she has succumbed to exhaustion after the dance in the Victorian tradition of the collapsing woman, her direct and longing gaze reveals her Dionysian nature. Still, *dolce far niente*, translated from Italian, means “carefree” or “the sweetness of doing nothing.” This evokes an idyllic vision of the ancient past analogous to Leighton’s. It also suggests that the longing gaze of Godward’s collapsed woman contains a non-sexual, psychospiritual — indeed, Apollonian — aspect. If so, Godward’s beauties and Leighton’s high art might be more than superficially similar.

Leighton’s work exhibits a timeless quality comparable to Godward’s. It has been seen that some of Leighton’s female figures, as in *Bath of Psyche*, are mythological subjects, but others, such as *Flaming June*, approach classical genre by depicting “everyday” subjects. According to Wood, Leighton found a respite from the heroic passion and drama of works such as *Perseus on Pegasus* in the beauty of the female form. “The mood is one of passive nostalgia and yearning for a lost world of classical beauty and order,” he wrote.³¹

Perhaps Godward’s women, whether their gazes avert inward or direct outward, reflect a similar mood. This wistfulness, which is a common characteristic not only of British classical-subject painting but also of Symbolism and Aestheticism, is communicated intuitively through the languor and detachment of the figures. It arouses in the viewer a sense of the eternal, which is a necessary component of ideal beauty.³²

In approaching this ideal, both Godward and Leighton were influenced by the styles of Renaissance artists. Wood observes that Victorian classical-subject painters, in search of a stylistic identity, commonly looked toward the “heroes” of the Italian

³⁰ Swanson, *Godward*, 76–77, 211.

³¹ Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 54.

³² “The very transitoriness of the moment which art has fixed ... excites a slight and quite specific pathos; for to fix the fleeting, ever-changing world ... seems to bring time itself to a standstill, for it raises the individual to the ... [archetype] of its species.” Schopenhauer, *Will and Idea*, 145.

Quattro- and Cinquecenti: Botticelli, Leonardo, Michelangelo, Raphael, Titian, Veronese and many others. “The Victorian vision of the classical tradition,” wrote Wood, “was expressed in the language of the Renaissance.”³³

Although all of Leighton’s women are Hellenic in subject or setting, they retain a vestige of the *figura serpentinata*, or quality of restless torsion, that descends directly from the manner of Michelangelo.³⁴ *Flaming June*, despite her languor, reveals several similarities to *The Delphic Sibyl* from the Sistine ceiling (fig. 49).³⁵ Each contorts her body and positions her limbs at sharp angles.³⁶ Each is foreshortened and shrouded in drapery, depending for completion upon the viewer’s imagination. Both are masculinised, with *Flaming June*’s powerful build recalling the muscularity of the Sibyl.

The frozen posture of the Sibyl embodies the Neo-Platonic idea of divine inspiration.³⁷ Indeed, the Sibyl’s meditations are transferred to her body by the passions, and she cannot hold her pose for long. Similarly, *Flaming June*’s dreams may awaken her from sleep at any moment. Whilst these two figures appear calm, their contortions and foreshortenings are symbolic of inner struggles, which inspire the viewer to ponder the eternal by recognising God in the potential for action.³⁸ Michelangelo’s Sibyl and Leighton’s *Flaming June* illustrate the Neo-Platonic idea

³³ Wood, *Olympian Dreamers*, 17.

³⁴ Erwin Panofsky, *Studies in Iconology: Humanistic Themes in the Art of the Renaissance* (1939; repr. London: Harper and Row, 1972), 174.

³⁵ The Sibyl is shown in reverse for easier comparison.

³⁶ The Sibyl rotates her head and torso horizontally and holds her right arm perpendicular to her body, whilst Leighton’s woman, in order to fit on her bench, has rotated her hips vertically and raised her left leg to support her left arm.

³⁷ According to Panofsky, the Renaissance humanist Marsilio Ficino (1433–99) conceived of the “rational soul [as] participating in the divine mind, but employing a body.” Panofsky, *Iconology*, 137.

³⁸ For more on this concept, originated by Giovanni Pico della Mirandola (1463–94) in *Oration on the Dignity of Man* (c. 1486), see Charles Seymour Jr., ed., *Michelangelo: The Sistine Chapel Ceiling: Illustrations, Introductory Essay, Backgrounds and Sources, Critical Essays* (New York: W.W. Norton & Company, 1972), 135.

that the “higher realms” of the soul inform the “lower realms” of the body.³⁹

Although Godward’s *A Siesta* is derivative of Leighton’s *Flaming June*, it is twice removed from Michelangelo. Only the faintest traces of the Michelangelesque remain in the curvature of the woman’s body and the gentle foreshortenings of her limbs and torso. With the easy folding of her left leg, she appears to fit comfortably on Godward’s bench; her pose retains none of the tension of Michelangelo’s figure. Instead, the fluidity of her posture is closer to the s-curve typical of Raphael’s female figures, such as *St. Catherine of Alexandria* from 1507–8 (fig. 50). Godward’s figure in *A Siesta* is one of his rarest in that her torso recedes into space. Most of his women remain present to the viewer in a distinct and shallow foreground, a format that resembles Renaissance Christian devotional imagery.

Many of Godward’s women seem to represent a secularisation of the type of saintly images found in Renaissance art. One example is 1893’s *Endymion* (fig. 51), whose pose echoes that of a Renaissance statue of the martyred St. Cecilia from an engraving in Jameson’s book (fig. 52).⁴⁰ As Gail-Nina Anderson and Joanne Wright observed in *Heaven on Earth*, Jameson’s illustrated saints and Madonnas significantly influenced the painters of the late-Victorian era:

The single figure, pulled out of pictorial context and represented in linear form as an engraving, could be curiously potent despite the paucity of its visual means. The female saint or Madonna thus becomes an isolated figure, a simplified, almost expressionless emblem of feminine grace, curiously robed and coiffed, carrying an attribute which is reduced by this process to a decorative accessory and yet still functioning as a sign ...⁴¹

Jameson herself had commented that Renaissance “shapes of beauty” had

³⁹ Deborah Vess’s essay borrows heavily from Panofsky. Deborah Vess, “The Influence of Neoplatonism on Michelangelo,” *The World Civilization Virtual Library*, <http://www.faculty.de.gsu.edu/~dvess/micel.htm> (accessed October 24, 2004).

⁴⁰ Jameson, *Sacred and Legendary*, 2: 588.

⁴¹ Anderson and Wright, *Heaven on Earth*, 22.

returned, even as the Victorians had “outgrown” the associations with Christian theology.⁴² Before Godward, Pre-Raphaelite and Symbolist painters had transferred the emotional and aesthetic qualities of female religious figures in Renaissance art to their own secular subjects. Rossetti’s *Beata Beatrix* of 1872 (fig. 53), for instance, depicts the rebirth of Dante’s saintly, enraptured Beatrice. The dove-like bird and lily-like flower are analogous to the Christian symbols of purity, whilst on the predella Dante meets Beatrice in Paradise.⁴³ Both Jameson and Rossetti haunted the Print Room at the British Museum, where they studied reproductions of the Old Italian Masters.⁴⁴

British classical-subject painters may have also frequented the Print Room to browse drawings after Raphael and other Renaissance painters. Drawings such as *Pensive Woman* (fig. 54) by Marcantonio Raimondi (c. 1475–1534), depicting a saintly female figure inspired by an angel, appear to be ancestors of the Victorian “waiting woman.” Echoes of these images carried over into Godward’s work. In *Le Billet Doux* of 1913 (fig. 55), for example, an earthly message from an unseen suitor substitutes for the heavenly message of a Renaissance angel. For Godward, perhaps, pensive Renaissance females inspired pensive classical beauties.

With the Aesthetic mode of visual representation, the secularised iconic image replaced the narrative moral allegory.⁴⁵ Thus, the Redeeming lion at the centre of multiple phrases of frozen action in *Israel in Egypt* relinquished its role to *The Fruit Vendor*’s lion, who became the companion-protector of ideal, unchanging beauty. Anderson and Wright describe the iconographic function of waiting, dreaming, or pondering women:

⁴² Jameson, *Sacred and Legendary*, 1: 6, 10.

⁴³ Maas, *Victorian Painters*, 138; Jameson, *Sacred and Legendary*, 1: 32.

⁴⁴ David A. Ludley, “Anna Jameson and D.G. Rossetti: His Use of Her Histories,” *Woman’s Art Journal* 12, No. 2 (Autumn 1991–Winter 1992): 33.

⁴⁵ Anderson and Wright, *Heaven on Earth*, 31.

[The figures indicate] moments of heightened awareness which require little in the way of expression or movement which might fracture the mood. The viewer is invited to enter a visionary world, intense and transcendent, where the motif ... is intended to partake of the eternal.⁴⁶

According to Anderson and Wright, Pre-Raphaelite and Symbolist painters borrowed from Renaissance antecedents to lend an air of tradition and legitimacy to their secular images of beauty. For these artists, “saints and angels were once again on the agenda, heavenly gardens of symbolic flowers could bloom again, yet theological meanings, which might trouble Protestant sensibilities, were suppressed.”⁴⁷ Scottish painter John Duncan’s (1866–1945) *Hymn to the Rose* of 1907 (fig. 56), for instance, is a secular interpretation of Botticelli’s *Madonna of the Pomegranate* of around 1487 (fig. 57).⁴⁸ In Duncan’s whimsical celebration of summer flowers, a rose plant replaces the Christ Child, and a central but secular female figure strikes a Madonna-like pose.⁴⁹ Duncan also imitated the painting’s circular format, or tondo.

One of the most distinctive characteristics of Godward’s *oeuvre* is his copious use of the tondo. The shape descends from a type of devotional imagery common in Quattrocento Florence, and enjoyed a surge of popularity during the Victorian era. Most tondi, both Florentine and Victorian, were intended for the embellishment of domestic interiors during a time of economic prosperity.⁵⁰ According to art historian Roberta J.M. Olson, the circular form of Florentine tondi “emphasised their heavenly content ...

⁴⁶ Anderson and Wright, *Heaven on Earth*, 31.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, 222.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, 74. Anderson and Wright liken Duncan’s painting to *Virgin and Child with St. John and Two Angels* (ca. 1487) attributed to the studio of Botticelli, perhaps because of its prominent roses. However, *Hymn to the Rose* is more compositionally similar to the famous *Madonna of the Pomegranate*, and it is likely that Duncan used this as his primary model.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ Roberta J.M. Olson, *The Florentine Tondo* (Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 2000), 3. A tondo provided its bourgeois Florentine homeowner with a convenient means of worship as well as the social certification that he was appropriately pious. Likewise, the prosperous Victorian patron certified his taste and social status by owning a secular tondo or other work.

it immediately connoted a sacred space within a more secular environment.”⁵¹

Godward’s tondi represent a similar relationship between the secular and the sacred.

Godward’s classically-draped woman in the tondo-shaped *Golden Hours* of 1913 (fig. 58) echoes the Michelangelesque pose of Raphael’s Virgin in *Madonna della Sedia* of 1513 (fig. 59).⁵² Olson observes that, at first glance, *Madonna della Sedia*, with her exotic headdress, intricate shawl, sumptuous surroundings, and casual pose, does not appear to be a Madonna.⁵³ To her, the painting comes off as a Christian “costume piece in which models were used,” and the Virgin’s turban-like headdress forms a kind of secular halo.⁵⁴ Similarly, Godward’s *Golden Hours* is a classical costume piece in which the halo is the model’s Japanese fan, held above her head. Perhaps Raphael’s Virgin appealed to Godward because her non-traditional appearance lent itself to easy secularisation.

Madonna della Sedia, in which the figures are superbly adapted to their circular format, represents the culmination of Raphael’s use of the tondo.⁵⁵ Godward’s secular beauty in *Golden Hours* retains little of the Michelangelesque *figura serpentinata*, thus conforming to her circle less ingeniously.⁵⁶ Still, Godward held the painting in such high regard that he inscribed “One of my Masterpieces” on the stretcher bar.⁵⁷ Swanson contends that Godward, in elevating his women to “embodiments of mythic perfection,” found in them his “personal nurturing Freudian

⁵¹ Olson, *Florentine Tondo*, 3.

⁵² Although Godward painted *Golden Hours* in Rome, Raphael’s *Madonna della Sedia* resides in Florence. Nonetheless, Raphael’s famous painting would have been familiar to Godward through numerous reproductions. Even the reproductions were reproduced, as in Kate Hayllar’s (exhibited 1883–1900) *A Thing of Beauty is a Joy Forever* of 1890, which features a framed print of *Madonna della Sedia* as the centrepiece of an arrangement of beautiful things.

⁵³ Olson, *Florentine Tondo*, 216.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵⁵ Konrad Oberhuber, ed., *The Illustrated Bartsch*, vol. 27 of *The Works of Marcantonio Raimondi and His School*, ed. Walter L. Strauss (New York: Abaris Books, 1978), 143.

⁵⁶ In Godward’s preparatory sketch for *Golden Hours*, the slighter angle of the model’s head and the absence of a circular guideline suggest that he only later decided to place her within the tondo.

⁵⁷ Swanson, *Godward*, 233.

madonna.”⁵⁸ Perhaps Godward cherished *Golden Hours*, with its secular halo and circular format, as the epitome of his devotion to the idealised female form.

Thus, in Godward’s secular adaptation of Raphael’s *Madonna della Sedia* without the Child and St. John, only the all-important Madonna remains. Conversely, Duncan’s symbolic interpretation of Botticelli’s *Madonna of the Pomegranate* preserves each element in its original relationship to the others. Botticelli’s tondo can be likened to a divine flower for which his angelic children are petals, and the central, upright Virgin forms the holy pistil.⁵⁹ In *Hymn to the Rose*, Duncan exchanged the symbols of Christian piety for their secular equivalents.

Olson argues that Florentine tondi had dual aspects. First, they functioned as metaphorical mirrors: they reflected the heavenly world whilst also inspiring the viewer to contemplate the inner world of his or her own soul.⁶⁰ In this sense, tondi embodied the Neo-Platonic belief that progress from the lower to higher realms of the soul depended upon the proper exertion of the individual will. Second, they functioned as oculi, or heavenly windows. As Olson believes, most tondi “allow the pious observer to engage in extreme empathetic contemplation of God to the point of oblivion and mystical union.”⁶¹ Godward’s tondi correspond primarily with this second aspect. Insofar as most of the artist’s women seem to inhabit “display windows,” his tondi might be considered analogous to portholes devoted to the secular worship of the incorruptible female form.

Where Godward’s phraseless tondi are *portholes* for viewing, it has been seen that some of his earlier multi-phrase works, similar to paintings by Alma-Tadema

⁵⁸ Swanson, *Godward*, 135.

⁵⁹ Guiseppe Fiocco, “A Newly Discovered Tondo by Botticelli,” *The Burlington Magazine for Connoisseurs* 57, No. 331 (October 1930): 53.

⁶⁰ Olson, *Florentine Tondo*, 105.

⁶¹ “Tondi were literally like windows into the heavenly realm because round windows or oculi were features of Florentine Renaissance architecture.” *Ibid.*, 3.

such as *The Frigidarium*, contain portals for entering. Indeed, the circular frame of the tondo is ill suited to the linear architecture and other archaeological objects that characterise much of Alma-Tadema's work. For Godward, however, the circle was a means of artistic liberation. It allowed him to eliminate most artefacts whilst maximising his figures' aesthetic potential. Godward did paint portrait-like busts such as *Classical Beauty* of 1908 (fig. 60) without artefacts in a standard rectangular format, but the visual impact of his tondi is generally greater.

Godward's *A Grecian Girl* of 1908 (fig. 61), for example, includes a narrow slice of obligatory marble carving; *In Realms of Fancy* of 1911 (fig. 62) contains only a hint of plain marble. Yet, the women within mold their bodies to the curvature of the circle. What art historian Konrad Oberhuber observes of Raphael's figures in *Madonna della Sedia* also applies to Godward's figures here: "Everything flows along swinging curves ... relating it to the round frame," he wrote, "in complete inner repose, a small, revolving cosmos."⁶² The tondo was the ideal format for what we might consider to be Godward's Apollonian archetype.

In a similar manner as Godward's secular images of classical beauties, Renaissance paintings of saints, the Madonna, and the Saviour rarely depict actions or events. Instead, as Schopenhauer believed, they reflect inner peace:

In their faces, and especially in the eyes, we see the expression, the reflection, of the most perfect knowledge, that which is directed not to particular things but has fully grasped the Ideas [i.e. the ideals], and thus the whole nature of the world and life. And this knowledge in them, reacting upon the will, does not, like other knowledge, convey motives to it, but on the contrary has become a *quieter* of all willing.⁶³

Like Renaissance saints and Madonnas, Godward's idealised Apollonian women, with their pensive expressions, languorous poses, and transcendental beauty,

⁶² Konrad Oberhuber, *Raphael: The Paintings* (New York: Prestel Verlag, 1999), 110.

⁶³ Schopenhauer, *Will and Idea*, 147.

also seem to quiet the will. Indeed, Swanson describes Godward's "patrician maidens" as "reserved, uncritical, and discreet . . . seldom disturb[ing] their serene environment," and the artist as "a desperate contriver of dream icons, symbolising the archetypal world of women, beauty and peace."⁶⁴ The tranquil demeanours of the women within these paintings run parallel to their Renaissance Christian counterparts, and particularly to images of Mary.

Renaissance images of Mary often include accoutrements of earthly kingship adapted to Christian purposes. Bellini's *Madonna and Child Blessing* of 1510 (fig. 63), for example, includes a royal "cloth of honour," the traditional symbol of nobility and triumph. In images of the Madonna, it refers to her queenship. As the late art historian Rona Goffen explained, however, it may have derived from a curtain in an ancient Hebrew sanctuary "that separated the outer sphere (where men came to worship) from the *sanctum sanctorum*," or Holy of Holies.⁶⁵ It functions as a supernatural veil marking the symbolic divide between the material realm and the heavenly kingdom.⁶⁶ Perhaps the marble walls behind Godward's pensive beauties are a secular equivalent to the Christian cloth of honour, marking the division between the material and the spiritual, the temporal and eternal.

⁶⁴ Swanson, *Godward*, 135; *Ibid.* 169–70.

⁶⁵ Rona Goffen, "Icon and Vision: Giovanni Bellini's Half-Length Madonnas," *The Art Bulletin* 57, No. 4 (December 1975): 497.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, 497–98.

CONCLUSION

Godward's focus on the female figure bears the mark of the late-Victorian and Edwardian trend toward Aestheticism. However, there are two reasons why his paintings of classical women cannot be described simply as art-for-art's sake. First, Godward's voluptuous women in paintings such as *The Mirror*, whilst superficially similar to the sculptural figures of Moore, are neither predominantly experimental nor purely decorative. Where Moore's austere figures are formal constructions, Godward's women exhibit a psychological dimension that engages the viewer's emotions. As Swanson observes, "Godward's art was not truly an aesthetic exercise, but rather art therapy masking a troubled soul."¹ Second, Godward's depictions of classical women, with their formulaic balance of sameness and variety, were calculated to please the British bourgeois male. This somewhat homogenous *oeuvre* was conducive to speedy production, suggesting a decidedly anti-Aesthetic financial motive.²

Godward's obsession with the idealised feminine form also had a levelling effect on his art; "perfection" varies little.³ The majority of Godward's women inhabit phraseless works that function as a kind of window or porthole in which the artist offered them up for display whilst also keeping them metaphorically pure. His early multi-phrase paintings contain doorways or portals by which the viewer engages with the figures by "entering" the scene.

These works from the 1880s and 90s, such as *Innocent Amusements*, exhibit

¹ Swanson here does not use "aesthetic" here as a proper name. Swanson, *Godward*, 170.

² There is truth to Swanson's contention that Godward did not "kowitz the critics or pander to the [general] public." As a bourgeois male himself, Godward could produce marketable work whilst also fulfilling his own psychosexual/psychospiritual yearnings; one did not necessarily negate the other. *Ibid.*, 134.

³ Godward's obsession with depictions of classical women "saturated his life to the exclusion of avocations, friends, and family." Swanson, *Godward*, 134.

Godward's concern with the momentary and particular of British classical genre. They show a strong affinity to Alma-Tadema's multi-phrase depictions of Imperial Rome. Since the phrases in these paintings imply either moral action or the potential for it, the role of the classical women within them reflects Victorian values regarding women's role in society. To further reinforce this domestic ideology, paintings such as Godward's *Sewing Girl* contain symbolic objects, the meanings of which depend upon their specific archaeological contexts.

As Godward moved gradually toward a more Aesthetic mode of composition, works such as *At the Thermae*, where action appears suspended, lack archaeologically-specific socio-material settings. Thus, the female figures such as the fruit vendor embody Godward's idea of a perfect, incorruptible, and apparently amoral archetype. *The Fruit Vendor's* lion, though reminiscent of Poynter's, is neither the Redeemer nor the Resurrection, but the secular guardian of feminine beauty.

Although grounded in classical genre, Godward sometimes borrowed the visual language of high art. Women in paintings such as *A Fair Reflection* and *Golden Hours*, derived from printed sources or inspired by the works of contemporaries, descend indirectly from Hellenic or Italian Renaissance forms. Although Godward has purged many of these figures of overt mythological or Christian associations, their fluidity of posture is the outward manifestation of inner peace. Paintings such as *Golden Hours*, analogous to Renaissance Christian devotional imagery, often take the perfect form of the tondo. The Apollonian maidens within these works represent a kind of soothing, secular madonna. In contrast, Godward's uninhibited Dionysian women gaze shamelessly toward the middle-class male viewer, tempting him to act upon his repressed psychosexual impulses. Coy yet titillating beauties appear midway, exhibiting an element of each. In any case, Godward's women generally lack the

Michelangesque *figura serpentinata* marking the inner moral struggles of Renaissance Neo-Platonism.

Unlike his friends Bulleid and Ryland, the repetitive Godward did not diversify his subject matter. Nonetheless, Bulleid and Ryland remain virtually unknown, whilst Godward has gained a modicum of respect as a highly-skilled painter of “dream icons.” These iconic images, whether pensive Apollonian, tempting Dionysian, or betraying aspects of both, are windows into the artist’s enigmatic psyche. As mutually opposing female types, they contain a Symbolist element. Devoid of any discernable moral or religious agenda, they are cousins of Aestheticism. They are not the mere trifles that Roger Fry would have assumed, but neither do they satisfy E.I. Barrington’s Christian sensibility. They are not intended to ennoble like the art of Leighton. Godward’s classical women, amoral archetypes representing the balance of the artist’s work, are meant instead to convey an essential, unchanging, and perfect beauty.

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